

Synthesis of the Mg-Fe-H system from different Fe sources

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Hamburg, den December 3, 2020

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Preface

This master thesis was written at the department for Nanotechnology and Hydrogen Technology at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht in cooperation with the Institute of Polymer and Composites of the Hamburg University of Technology.

Vorwort

Diese Masterarbeit entstand in der Abteilung für Nanotechnologie und Wasserstofftechnik am Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht in Kooperation mit dem Institut für Kunststoffe und Verbundwerkstoffe an der Technischen Universität Hamburg.

Abstract

The synthesis of the Mg-Fe-H system with different Fe sources is investigated in this work. Different characterisation techniques are employed to obtain further insight on the impact of the steels 316L and M300 as Fe source on the system. It is found, that the steels have a positive impact on the kinetic behaviour. Nevertheless, the reached capacity is lower than that of the system synthesised with pure Fe. Theoretical physical models are used to fit to the experimental data. Consequently, the rate limiting step can be identified. Additionally *in situ* PXD measurements were performed, to investigate the systems during the absorption and desorption processes. This technique allows to get further insight into the phase building and transformation processes. Furthermore, a room temperature absorption could be observed, which is the first time that the formation of MgH_2FeH_6 is reported to occur under such mild temperature conditions. The results presented in this work show a first approach to employ waste material in the development of hydrogen and heat storage systems to assist in the transition to a more sustainable world.

Kurzfassung

In folgender Masterarbeit wird die Synthese des Mg-Fe-H Systems näher betrachtet. Verschiedene Charakterisierungsmethoden kommen dabei zum Einsatz, um Einblicke in den Einfluss der Stähle auf das System zu bekommen. Eine Erkenntnis ist, dass die Stähle einen positiven Effekt auf das kinetische Verhalten haben. Nichtsdestotrotz ist die erreichte gravimetrische Kapazität geringer, als bei der Referenzprobe. Theoretische Modelle werden genutzt, um die begrenzenden Prozesse beziehungsweise Reaktionen bestimmen zu können. *In situ* Röntgendiffraktometrie ermöglicht Einblicke in das Absorptions- und Desorptionsverhalten, sowie der Phasenbildung und -entwicklung. Eine Absorption bei Raumtemperatur konnte beobachtet werden, welches für MgH_2FeH_6 unter so milden Temperaturbedingungen zuvor noch nicht berichtet wurde. Die in dieser Arbeit vorgestellten Ergebnisse weisen einen ersten Ansatz auf, um recyceltes Material in die Entwicklung von Wasserstoff- und Wärmespeichersystemen zu integrieren.

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Nomenclature and Abbreviations

Nomenclature

Latin Characters

Character	Unit	Meaning
A	$\frac{1}{s}$	Pre-exponential Factor
d	mm	Diameter
E_a	$\frac{J}{mol}$	Activation Energy
H	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	Enthalpy
ΔH	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	Reaction Enthalpy
k	$\frac{1}{s}$	Kinetic Constant
K	-	Equilibrium Constant
m	kg	Mass
M	-	Metal
n	mol	Amount of Substance
N	-	Number of balls
p	bar	Pressure
P^*	Wh	Transfer Energy
Q	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$ H ₂	Heat
r	m	Radius
R	$\frac{J}{molK}$	Universal Gas Constant
S	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	Entropy
ΔS	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	Reaction Entropy
t	s	Time
T	°C	Temperature
V	cm^3	Volume
x	wt-%	Absorbed Amount of Hydrogen

Greek Characters

Character	Unit	Meaning
α	-	Reacted Fraction
β	$\frac{\text{K}}{\text{min}}$	Heating Rate
θ	$^{\circ}$	Angle
λ	m or \AA	Wavelength
ρ	$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{m}^3}$	Density
Ω	$\frac{\text{rad}}{\text{s}}$	Rotation speed
ω	$\frac{\text{rad}}{\text{s}}$	Rotation velocity

Indices

Index	Meaning
b	ball
c	critical
dec	decomposition
hkl	Miller indices
p	powder
p	peak
p	plate
r	reference
v	vial

Chemical Elements

Index	Meaning
Ag	Silver
Al	Aluminum
Ar	Argon
C	Carbon
Ca	Calcium
Cu	Copper
Co	Cobalt
Cr	Chromium
Fe	Iron
Mg	Magnesium
Mn	Manganese
Mo	Molybdenum
N	Nitrogen
Nb	Niobium
Nd	Neodymium
Ni	Nickel
P	Phosphorus
S	Sulphur
Si	Silicon
Ta	Tantalum
Ti	Titanium
V	Vanadium
Y	Yttrium
Zn	Zinc

Abbreviations

Abbrev.	Meaning
AFC	Alkaline Fuel Cell
DESY	Deutsches Elektronen Synchrotron
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DMFC	Direct Methanol Fuel Cell
DTA	Differential Thermal Analyses
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-Ray
FFT	Fast-Fourier-Transformation
FTIR	Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
HCP	Hexagonal Closed-Packed
HZG	Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht
ICSD	Inorganic Crystal Structure Database
MCFC	Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell
MH	Metal Hydride
MS	Mass Spectroscopy
PAFC	Phosphoric Acid Fuel Cell
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
PCI	Pressure Composition Isotherm
PCT	Pressure Composition Temperature
PEMFC	Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell
PMMA	Poly-Methyl-Methacrylate
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
PXD	Powder X-Ray Diffraction
RBM	Reactive Ball Milling
rpm	Revolutions per Minute
RT	Room Temperature
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
SR-PXD	Synchrotron-Radiation Powder X-Ray Diffraction
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
TM	Transition Metal
TUHH	Technical University of Hamburg
VASP	The Vienna <i>Ab Initio</i> Simulation Package
VESTA	Visualisation for Electronic and Structural Analysis
wt	Weight
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction

1 Introduction

The world's population has increased from approximately 1.65 billion in 1900 to 7.7 billion people in 2019 [1]. This significant growth, as well as the ongoing electrification of large industrial sectors, led to an even more drastically increase in the world's energy demand. Thus, the overall energy consumption in 2019 was approximately 13 times higher compared to 1900, as can be seen in Figure 1.1 [2].

Figure 1.1: Global direct primary energy consumption [2]

Nowadays more than 80% of the global energy demand is fulfilled by the combustion of fossil fuels. The use of such energy sources led to disruptive climate changes that threatens the life on earth [3]. Global warming, as a result of higher CO₂ levels, has a devastating effect on nature and the whole ecosystem on our planet [4]. The need for sustainability and environmental protection makes the search for clean and safe energy alternatives a major necessity [3]. However, the shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources leads to the challenge of storing large quantity of energy from sources that are intermittent and unevenly distributed on earth [5]. In this regard, the possibility to store energy via hydrogen is foreseen as a potential solution to tackle this epochal transition [3, 6]. In fact, hydrogen can be produced in an environmentally friendly manner via water electrolysis

using the energy provided by solar, aeolian, tidal and geothermal energy sources. These energy sources can be utilised to power an electrolyser that generates hydrogen [7]. The basic concept is portrayed in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Basic concept of electrolysis via renewable energy sources [7]

In the course of water electrolysis, the water molecules are broken down into their two components hydrogen and oxygen [6]. In Equation (1.1), the process taking place in a water electrolyser is summarised [8].

Nevertheless, the use of hydrogen as an energy storage medium requires the development of technologies that allow an efficient and safe storage of the hydrogen itself. In developing these technologies, aspects such as reliability, as well as flexibility of use are also considered [3]. A concise introduction on the hydrogen storage methods is provided in Section 2.1.

The environmentally friendliness of hydrogen as energy storage medium is bonded to the possibility to retrieve the energy contained in it by using electrochemical cell devices. Such devices are the so called fuel cells that allow converting the chemical free energy of hydrogen into electrical energy [9]. One of the most broad classification of the fuel cells is based on the employed electrolyte material, e.g. polymer electrolyte membrane fuel

cells (PEMFC), direct methanol fuel cells (DMFC), alkaline fuel cells (AFC), phosphoric acid fuel cells (PAFC), molten carbonate fuel cells (MCFC), solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) and reversible fuel cells [10]. By displaying a broad range of power outputs, operating temperatures and electrical efficiencies, the different types of fuel cells are suitable for a variety of applications. The most suitable type of fuel cells for mobile application, e.g. the automotive sector, is the PEMFC. This is mostly due to the working temperatures that are of about 80°C and to the possibility to adapt its design to the targeted environment [11].

The functioning principle of fuel cells is similar to that of batteries. A PEMFC consist of a cathode, an anode and an electrolyte membrane that separates the reactants [9, 12]. Hence, the fuel and the air are segregated. For the discussed process, the driving force is the Gibbs free energy of the following Equation (1.2) [9].

The schematic process of a PEMFC is illustrated in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Basic concept of a PEMFC [13]

In a fuel cell, the fundamental operations are the flow of hydrogen through the anode and the flow of oxygen through the cathode [9, 12]. When the hydrogen is split into protons and electrons at the anode, solely the protons pass through the membrane and

the electrons are forced through a circuit leading to waste heat and electric current [9, 12]. On the other side of the cell, at the cathode, water is generated from oxygen, the protons and the electrons [9, 12].

One of the most promising application of hydrogen in the transportation sector is connected to automotive applications. Compared to a common internal combustion engine running on gasoline with an energetic efficiency of $\sim 22\%$, or running on diesel with an energetic efficiency of $\sim 45\%$, a fuel cell is, to a huge extent, with over 60%, way more efficient. Particularly for automotive applications, the employment of hydrogen driven fuel cells is advantageous over the use of battery cells [14]. In terms of the driving range, a fuel cell car running on hydrogen compressed to 700 bar (5 kg H_2), has an autonomy that lays in between 300 to 700 km [15–18]. The German car manufacturer Mercedes Benz successfully built a car which is powered by a combination of a battery pack (a Li-ion battery) and a fuel cell. Thus, the car is totally emission free during use [19]. However, also other manufacturers, like Hyundai and Honda, introduced fuel cell cars successfully into the market [16, 17]. The Toyota Mirai was introduced into the market in 2015 and is, in terms of the storage capacity, able to power a household for a week [15]. The concept of the Toyota Mirai is equivalent to the Mercedes-Benz GLC F-Cell, yet they use a nickel-MH battery for the energy storage as can be seen in Figure 1.4.

Fuel cell electric technology explained

Figure 1.4: Concept of the Toyota Mirai [15]

In the following Table 1.1, a comparison between a Toyota Mirai, a Honda Clarity, a Hyundai Nexo and a Mercedes GLC F-Cell is drawn. The values coloured in green are the most favourable out of the four vehicles. Toyota is the only manufacturer using a metal hydride system for storage [15]. In terms of range, Hyundai is superior to the other manufacturers with a range of over 700 km [17]. Nevertheless, it also has the highest consumption of all of the displayed cars and the heaviest and highest storage mass and volume with almost 6.5 kg and a 156.6 L tank [17]. The Mercedes Benz provides the highest maximum power, however, it is also a larger model than the other three [18]. On top of that, factors like refuelling time also depend on the size of the battery.

Table 1.1: Comparison of different fuel cell cars [16–18, 20]

	Toyota Mirai	Honda Clarity	Hyundai Nexo	Mercedes-Benz GLC F-Cell
Battery	Ni-metal hydride	Li-ion	Li-ion	Li-ion
Tank Volume /L	122.4	141.0	156.6	?
H ₂ Storage /kg	5.00	5.00	6.33	4.40
Refueling Time /min.	5	3	5	3
Consumption /kg $\frac{\text{H}_2}{100\text{km}}$	0.76	0.77	1.20	1.01
Range /km	480	650	750	328
Max. Speed $\frac{\text{km}}{\text{h}}$	178	165	179	160
Acceleration 0-100 $\frac{\text{km}}{\text{h}}/\text{s}$	9.6	9.0	9.2	?
Max. Power /kW	114	130	120	155

Owing to the high volumetric hydrogen storage densities, the low energy consumption as well as low requirements to the needed infrastructure and safety, the scope of research has shifted to material-based hydrogen storage [21]. Metal hydrides (MH) can be formed with a variety of different materials where hydrogen is stored via adsorption, bulk-absorption, or chemical interaction (e.g. binary and complex hydrides) [21]. Since there are a lot of different MH systems that can be synthesised, MHs are accomodatable for different applications, making this method for storing hydrogen and providing it to a fuel cells very promising [21]. Additionally, the Mg-Fe-H systems, in the form of Mg₂FeH₆, is a complex hydride and known for its high volumetric hydrogen storage density and potentially low costs [9]. Consequently, MH systems, which are known since the 70's, have been further developed over the last twenty years and utilised e.g. in power back-up units and have been first implemented as storage system for submarines in 2003 [3, 22].

As of today, aeroplane manufacturers are developing new planes and technologies with hydrogen as the main fuel source, whereas for drones there are some manufacturers who already use hydrogen as their main power source [23]. A major breakthrough in the

aerospace sector was the successful take off of a four seater plane in 2016 in Germany fuelled entirely by hydrogen [24].

Nonetheless, there are still challenges in the application and use of storage materials for hydrogen. On the one hand side, the efficiency of storage application is still not good enough for most applications [9]. On the other hand, looking at applications in the automotive sector, there is a lack of hydrogen loading stations which hinders the use of cars powered by fuel cells [9]. These examples demonstrate that there is an existing need for further development and research in the field of renewable energy sources and storage. Therefore, the rising demand in energy has to be satisfied in a emission-free and safe way. The shift of using fossil fuels to alternative options is taking place right now and technologies, like fuel cells, can assist this transition.

2 Theoretical Background

In this chapter, the most common methods used to store hydrogen are discussed. Special emphasis is put on describing the storage of hydrogen in solid state via the formation of metal hydrides. Furthermore, the processes for material synthesis and according characterisation techniques are described.

2.1 Hydrogen Storage Concepts

Hydrogen, based on the target application, can be stored either using physical or chemical methods. This leads to the possibility to store hydrogen in gaseous form, liquid form or solid form. Examples are given in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Storage of Hydrogen; adapted from [10]

Hydrogen can be stored via physical methods in compressed form, liquid form at cryogenic temperature or compressed at cryogenic temperature. The chemical methods to store hydrogen take advantage of the possibility to store hydrogen into adsorbents, liquid organic carriers, interstitial hydrides and complex hydrides [3, 10].

Nowadays, the most commonly utilised hydrogen storage method, mainly for mobile applications, is the storage as compressed gas in tanks or vessels, at pressures up to 700 bar

at 20 °C [25, 26]. In this case, the achieved gravimetric energy density depends on the material which is used for the containers [26]. In order to reduce the overall system weight, the hydrogen tanks are often made out of carbon-based composite fibres. These fibres have the advantage of being extremely light weight with high hydrogen permeation resistance and high strength (up to ten times stronger than steel) [25, 26]. However, these fibres are also rather expensive (e.g. 80 – 150 $\frac{\$}{\text{kg}}$).

The compression process allows improving the volumetric energy density of hydrogen, however, even at 700 bar its energy density is still drastically lower than those of the most common fossil fuels. As an example it can be mentioned that at a pressure of 700 bar gaseous hydrogen possesses a volumetric energy density of about 5.6 $\frac{\text{MJ}}{\text{L}}$, whereas gasoline and diesel have energy densities which are more than 5.7 times larger [10]. However, fossil fuels possess the big disadvantage of being non-renewable energy sources. The problem with the compressed gas storage is related to the use of specially designed equipment, and to the potential risks that the handling of an highly pressurised flammable gas entails [25, 26]. As of today, a solution for a fast and safe refilling of cylinders, for the portable storage and transportation, is still missing [26]. Furthermore, the production cost of high pressure tanks and refilling stations is rather high [25].

Another possibility to store hydrogen is in the liquefied form. Compared with the compressed gas form (30 $\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ under 700 bar), this solution leads to a higher hydrogen storage density of 70 $\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ at 1 bar and 20 K. The main drawback of this option is the requirement of cooling the gas down to 20 K, due to the fact that the liquefaction temperature of hydrogen lays in the range of 20 – 25 K. Moreover, the losses due to the boiloff are a major inconvenience. Owing to the low temperatures, the vessels require a well designed insulation in order to prevent hydrogen loss [25, 26]. This is a reason for the research to focus on the insulation and cooling methods for liquid hydrogen storage, nowadays [26]. The amount of energy that is needed to liquefy hydrogen is very high and in fact up to 40 % of the lower heating value is consumed during this process. Typically the process consists of several cycles of compression, cooling and expansion [25]. Liquid hydrogen storage was initially developed for space vehicles and has been used for several years now [25, 26]. However, high initial costs for the production of liquid hydrogen and low temperatures render it an inconvenient storage method for fuel cell-powered vehicles [26].

The third main storage option is the storage in solid form, which provides an effective alternative to obtain high storage volumetric densities in a compact and safe way [25–27]. The main advantage of storing hydrogen in a solid form, i.e. hydride, is the near-ambient pressure conditions with almost no loss of hydrogen over long periods [3, 25, 27, 28]. The energy density of a solid state hydrogen storage system is based on the reduced inter-atomic distance that can be achieved when chemical bonds, different from H-H bonds,

(e.g. M-H, with M = metal) are formed. Thus, a significant increment of the energy storage density can be achieved. Hydrogen can form hydride species with several different metals (e.g. Na, Mg, Al) [26]. The high affinity of hydrogen for metals, leads to the breaking of the H-H bonds and the formation of M-H bonds. The formation reaction of a metal hydride is accompanied by the release of energy in the form of heat (i.e. Q), see (2.1).

Some of the best known hydrogen storage systems are the so called interstitial hydrides. In this materials, atomic hydrogen occupies the tetrahedral and octahedral interstitial spaces in the metal lattice. As a consequence of the occupied interstitial spaces, a swelling of the metal lattice is usually observed [26, 29]. These hydrides can operate reversibly at room temperature (RT) and atmospheric pressure. Despite the favourable operating conditions, they possess a limited gravimetric density between 1 to 3 wt%.

In (2.1) the M stands for a generic metal, the x for a fraction and MH_x is for the hydride. The Q is the released heat and usually is expressed as $\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \text{H}_2$. In Figure 2.2, a schematic process of the formation of metal hydrides is displayed.

Figure 2.2: Schematic of chemisorption [26]

As a first step, the hydrogen approaches the surface of the metal and is drawn closer by van der Waals forces [26, 30]. This phenomena is also called physisorption and confines the hydrogen in a space adjacent to the metal surface [3, 26]. During the so-called chemisorption, the hydrogen is adsorbed on the metal surface and forms a metal-hydrogen

bond [26]. Chemisorbed hydrogen diffuses into the interstitial sites of the metal lattice sites and forms a solid solution, the α -phase. When a certain concentration of hydrogen in a certain volume is reached, a new phase, called β -phase or metal hydride, starts to form [26]. This phase has a characteristic atomic metal-hydrogen ratio and the growth of the phase at the interface of the α and the β -phase goes on until the transformation to β is completed. A very common way to describe the above mentioned process is through the use of Pressure-Composition-Temperature (PCT) isotherms under isobaric conditions, as can be seen in Figure 2.3 [3, 26].

Figure 2.3: Pressure composition isotherm for hydrogen absorption with Van't Hoff plot on the right hand side [26]

This is a way of representing the hydrogen absorption process with respect to the applied hydrogen pressure and temperature conditions. On top of that, it provides a powerful method to obtain information on key parameters such as enthalpy and entropy variations associated to the hydride formation [3]. It is noteworthy, that the curvature of the section of PCT describing the α to β transition is nearly flat, thus indicating that this transition occurs under isobaric conditions. Moreover, this graph shows that an increase of the applied temperature leads to a shift of the α to β transition PCT plateau to higher pressures. It shows the solid solution (α -phase) on the left hand side of the isothermal region, the hydride phase (β -phase), which is on the right hand side of the isothermal region and a region of coexistence of the two phases with its horizontal plateau ending at the critical temperature T_c [3, 26].

Due to the fact that in most cases the pressure is not constant under equilibrium conditions, during the transformation from α to β , the graph shows a slope. This graph, as well as the concept of the slope of the plateau and the hysteresis phenomenon, has been described for interstitial hydrides and extended to chemical hydrides. The slope of the plateau can be attributed to several factors. One of them is the discontinuous growth of the lattice with the hydrogen concentration, leading to the interaction of H-H atoms [31]. Moreover, a possible cause of the plateau can also be ascribed to the non-homogeneous state of the sample as well as possible contamination. Additionally, the equilibrium pressure of the absorption tends to be higher than the equilibrium pressure in the desorption. This phenomenon is called hysteresis. As of today, there is no clear proof of the origin, but it is attributed to the modification of the stability of the phases, which is taking place due to relaxation and strain phenomena [31]. In the case of the Mg-Fe-H system, it is common that both MgH_2 and Mg_2FeH_6 are formed upon hydrogenation. As experimental evidence, the presence of the two hydride phases increases the hysteresis phenomenon since both species present different dehydrogenation equilibrium pressures [32].

The enthalpy and entropy variations associated to the hydride formation (or decomposition) can be obtained via the Van't Hoff's equation and the Van't Hoff plot, respectively, as shown in Equation (2.2) and Figure 2.4 [26]. The Van't Hoff Equation (2.2) describes the relation between the temperature T , the pressure p , the reaction entropy ΔS and the reaction enthalpy ΔH ,

$$\ln(p) = \frac{\Delta H}{RT} - \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (2.2)$$

with the gas constant R [26]. For solid-gas reactions the equilibrium constant reduces to the pressure of gas [26].

The reaction enthalpy is given by the slope of the plot and the entropy is represented by the intercept (with the y-axes) of the linear fit of the plot [26]. Usually, the enthalpy is given as a negative value because the reaction is exothermic. Hence, the dehydrogenation needs the according positive amount as energy input. The reaction enthalpy should remain small in order for the hydride to take up heat from surroundings, while releasing hydrogen at RT (since most applications run at RT). The obtained values of enthalpy and entropy variation allow determining the p - T dependence of a hydride, thus defining the practical operating conditions of a metal hydride system. Additionally, the enthalpy variation represents the strength of the M-H bonds and the variation of the entropy represents the change of entropy for the hydrogen transitioning from the gaseous form to the solid phase [26].

Figure 2.4: Van't Hoff plots of different hydrides [26]

2.2 Hydrogen Storage in Mg-Based Compounds

Aiming at finding suitable systems, which will allow to store large quantity of energy, researchers are intensively studying the possibility to utilise metal hydrides as hydrogen storage [3, 30, 33]. As described by the [U.S. Department of Energy](#), there are several requirements that potential candidate materials, for hydrogen storage applications, must fulfil at the commercial level. First of all, the hydride system should possess a relatively high hydrogen storage capacity of ~ 4.5 wt%, as well as good reversibility [10]. On top of that, the chosen material should display sufficient cyclic stability in order to be utilised over a high number of hydrogen desorption/absorption cycles without incurring significant losses of hydrogen storage capacity. Low costs of the raw materials and of the production process are additional aspects to be taken into consideration when deciding which system to choose for large scale commercial applications. Finally, the chosen system should meet high safety standards [3, 26].

In the last decades, Mg and Mg-based materials have been intensively studied as potential hydrogen storage materials. The first report on the possibility to hydrogenate Mg was published in 1951 by [Wiberg et al.](#). The reaction between Mg and hydrogen can be described as it follows [3, 33]:

One mole of Mg reacts exothermically with one mole of molecular hydrogen to form one mole of MgH_2 . Owing to the light weight of Mg, MgH_2 possesses a gravimetric hydrogen capacity of ~ 7.6 wt% and a volumetric hydrogen storage capacity of $110 \text{ kg } \frac{\text{H}_2}{\text{m}^3}$ [3, 30, 33].

Under ambient conditions, depending on the preparation method, magnesium hydride (MgH_2) crystallises in two polymorphic forms [3, 30]. The first one is the α - MgH_2 , which forms at ambient conditions and has a tetragonal TiO_2 rutile-type structure, as shown in Figure 2.5a) [3, 30]. The second form occurs at pressures > 3.9 kbar and is a metastable γ - MgH_2 , which crystallises with an orthorhombic α - PbO_2 structure. This phase can also be observed under ambient pressure conditions as the consequence of intensive mechanical treatment (e.g. ball milling).

During the hydrogenation, the metal lattice of magnesium expands by $\sim 30\%$ and leads to a transformation of an HCP (hexagonal closed-packed) metal sublattice into a deformed body-centred cubic sublattice. The MgH_2 structure is considered an insertion-type compound. The hydrogen atoms, due to being relatively small, are placed in the metal sublattice of Mg [3, 30].

Figure 2.5: Crystal Structures of Mg and MgH_2

Despite, the relatively high hydrogen storage capacity of MgH_2 , its high thermodynamic stability and the slow hydrogenation and dehydrogenation kinetics place some limitations to the widespread use of this system as hydrogen storage material. In fact, MgH_2 displays an equilibrium temperature for an ambient hydrogen pressure of $T(1 \text{ bar})=283^\circ\text{C}$ [3, 30, 33]. This value is calculated from the enthalpy and entropy change reported for bulk MgH_2 according to

$$\Delta H_{\text{dec}} = 74.06 \pm 0.42 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$\Delta S_{\text{dec}} = 133.4 \pm 0.7 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \quad (2.4)$$

[30]. The index "dec" is an abbreviation for decomposition. From the kinetic point of view, one of the biggest barriers to overcome in hydrogenation is the poor hydrogen dif-

fusivity through MgH_2 [3]. Thus, after a certain amount of magnesium hydride has been formed, the hydrogen diffusion rate through the hydrogenated layer slows down and even stops when a critical layer thickness is reached [3, 30, 33]. Several strategies for tuning the kinetic and thermodynamic properties of MgH_2 can be used.

Considerable enhancements of the kinetic properties of MgH_2 can be achieved by the employment of the ball milling technique. It allows refining the crystalline size of MgH_2 to the nanometer range, thus shortening the hydrogen diffusion paths in the material. The main drawback of this technique is that the kinetic enhancements tend to disappear over dehydrogenation/rehydrogenation cycling at high temperatures. More durable enhancement can be obtained by doping the MgH_2 with small quantities of transition metal (TM) based additives (e.g. Ni, Ti, TiO_2 , Nb_2O_5 etc.). In fact, the presence of finely well dispersed additives (via ball milling) leads to fast hydrogenation dehydrogenation kinetics and, by preventing massive grain coarsening phenomena, increases the cyclability of MgH_2 [3, 30, 33]. However, the additional weight, due to the presence of the additives, reduces the overall gravimetric capacity of the system (since additives do not absorb hydrogen themselves) [30].

From the thermodynamic point of view, an approach largely utilised in the metal hydride field is to alloy the starting metal with one or more additional species which possess different affinities for hydrogen. Thus, the resulting systems will possess thermodynamic properties intermediate between the starting metal and the alloying species. Examples of such an approach involving Mg are the Mg-Ni and the Mg-Cu systems. Compared with pure Mg, for the alloys of Mg-Ni and of Mg-Cu, the hydrogenation reaction enthalpy is significantly reduced. Consequently, the expected dehydrogenation reaction occurs at lower temperatures (at 1 bar hydrogen pressure 280 °C for pure MgH_2 , 250 °C for Mg_2NiH_4 and 240 °C for MgH_2 in the system Mg-Cu-H) [33].

Although not forming an intermetallic compound with Mg, the addition of Fe to the Mg-H system has been also investigated. The obtained Mg-Fe-H system possesses a gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity of 5.47 wt% and the reaction enthalpy associated to the hydrogenation process is $77 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \text{H}_2$.

In the following Table 2.1 different hydrides are displayed with their corresponding characteristics, where Mg_2FeH_6 is coloured in grey [33].

Mg_2NiH_4 and Mg_2FeH_6 are commonly referred to as complex metal hydrides. Owing to their high hydrogen storage capacities, mainly the volumetric capacity, complex metal hydrides gained attention as a potential hydrogen and heat storage both for mobile and stationary applications, as well as energy storage media owing to the relative high enthalpy values [14, 35, 36]. They connect both energy production and storage of the hydrogen

Table 2.1: Mg-based metal hydrides for hydrogen and heat storage [33]

Material	Hydrogen wt%	ΔH kJ/mol H ₂	Heat storage density kWh/kg	Equilibrium T at 1 bar /°C
MgH ₂	7.70	74.00	0.78	280
Mg-Cu-H	2.60	70.00	-	240
Mg ₂ NiH ₄	3.60	62.00	0.31	250
Mg ₂ FeH ₆	5.50	77.00	0.55	320

economy [3, 33]. Usually they are stoichiometric and nonmetallic and the term complex comes from the presence of discrete metal-hydrogen ligands inside the crystal structure [27]. Either a metal hydrogen complex (e.g. [FeH₆]⁴⁻, [NiH₄]⁴⁻) bonded to a transition or cationic alkali metal or an anionic non-metal hydrogen complex (e.g. [NH₂]⁻, [BH₄]⁻) are present.

The Mg-Fe hydride is known to have one of the highest volumetric hydrogen densities of $150 \frac{\text{kgH}_2}{\text{m}^3}$ and possesses a moderate gravimetric storage density of 5.47 wt%, as can be seen in Figure 2.6 [3, 27, 33, 37–39].

Figure 2.6: Volumetric and gravimetric density of hydrogen storage technologies [40]

For the formation of Mg₂FeH₆ the starting reactants are relatively inexpensive and thus the implementation of this compound in large scale applications is economically advantageous [3, 30, 33]. As previously mentioned, intermetallic phases of Mg and Fe do not exist, as can be seen in Figure 2.7. This is due to the positive energy of mixing between Mg and

Fe. The coexistence of Mg and Fe in Mg_2FeH_6 is possible due to the stabilisation induced by the presence of the hydrogen atoms. Mg_2FeH_6 forms by the reaction of magnesium hydride with iron at high temperatures in hydrogen atmosphere $T > T_{\text{dec}}(\text{MgH}_2)$ [3, 33]. The reaction scheme for MgH_2 -Fe in a ratio of 2 : 1 in a temperature range of $T = 380 - 470^\circ\text{C}$ and a hydrogen pressure of $p(\text{H}_2) = 1000$ bar is given by Equation (2.5):

In situ X-Ray diffraction with synchrotron-radiation (SR-PXD) analyses of the hydrogenation process led to the conclusion that for the applied temperature conditions, which are necessary to have sufficiently fast formation kinetics, the applied hydrogen pressure prevents the decomposition of MgH_2 and therefore enables the formation of Mg_2FeH_6 [33]. Heating Mg_2FeH_6 in Ar atmosphere with a pressure of $p(\text{Ar}) = 1$ bar leads to the decomposition reaction

which is in agreement with $T_{\text{dec}}(\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6) > T_{\text{dec}}(\text{MgH}_2)$ and the decomposition enthalpy of $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6 = 87 \pm 3 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \text{H}_2$ [33]. Although the high stability of Mg_2FeH_6 represents a barrier to its employment in mobile application, such as automotive, its utilisation in stationary applications (i.e. thermal energy storage) appears to be promising. High temperature thermo-chemical gas-solid systems are suitable for long-term, as well as short-term, solar energy storage. The short-term storage requires good kinetics of the absorption and desorption of the gaseous phase and a good heat conductivity of the reaction bed. The energy can be accessed and used at any time without losing a significant amount of it [33].

An advantage of reversible Mg-based metal hydrides is the high energy density in the range of $62 - 77 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \text{H}_2$. Nowadays, research focuses on materials for heat storage at $T \leq 550^\circ\text{C}$ for solar tower plants. I.e. , the following $2\text{Mg}+\text{Fe}/\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6$ system with the reaction scheme:

The identification of cost-effective materials with a high degree of reversibility upon multiple cycles and fast and controllable kinetics are crucial for this type of application [33].

Figure 2.7: Phase Diagram of the Mg-Fe system [41]

Owing to their high energy storage densities, good reversibility, and low cost, magnesium-iron-hydride and mixed $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-MgH}_2$ hydride system are considered suitable candidates for thermo-chemical thermal energy storage at a temperature of about 500°C [37, 38, 42, 43]. The structure of Mg_2FeH_6 is displayed in Figure 2.8, where iron lays in the centre of the unit cell.

Figure 2.8: Structure of Mg_2FeH_6 [43]

Investigating the hydrogenation mechanism, Bogdanovic et al. observed via transmission electron microscopy - energy dispersive X-Ray (TEM-EDX; TEM coupled with EDX method) that under dynamic temperature conditions the growth of Mg_2FeH_6 particles occurs by insertion of freshly formed Mg_2FeH_6 layers at the phase boundary between

iron seeds and the growing Mg_2FeH_6 phase. Thereby, the growth process provides a vermicular form of the Mg_2FeH_6 particles which appears to be stable even for hundreds of hydrogenation/dehydrogenation cycles [37]. Furthermore, he drew a comparison of the $\text{MgH}_2\text{-Mg}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-2Mg+Fe}$ system with calculated and experimental data as shown in Table 2.2. From the data in the table, it is visible that the weight related heat storage densities of $\text{MgH}_2\text{-Mg}$ and the $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-2Mg+Fe}$ systems are close to each other, while the volumetric heat storage density of the $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-2Mg+Fe}$ system is considerably higher than that of the $\text{MgH}_2\text{-Mg}$ system [37].

Table 2.2: Comparison of $\text{MgH}_2\text{-Mg}$ and the $\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-2Mg+Fe}$ system as reversible thermo-chemical heat storage media [37]

	$\text{MgH}_2\text{-Mg}$	$\text{Mg}_2\text{FeH}_6\text{-2Mg+Fe}$	Units
Reaction enthalpy (ΔH)	74.0	77.4	$\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$
Calculated hydrogen/heat storage capacity	7.66	5.47	wt% H_2
Experim. hydrogen heat storage capacity	6	5	wt% H_2
Theoretical density of the hydride	1.42	2.74	$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$
Experim. realised density of the hydride	0.80	1.22	$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$
Calculated heat storage density to weight	2814.0	2105.5	$\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$
Experim. heat storage density to weight	2204	1921	$\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$
Calculated heat storage density to volume	3996	5758	$\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{dm}^3}$
Experim. heat storage density to volume	1763	2344	$\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{dm}^3}$

The material can be synthesised via different procedures leading to yields of 25 – 90% [27, 37]. Bogdanovic et al. discovered that there are two different equilibrium pressures for the dehydrogenation process and that the higher one belongs to MgH_2 . The existence of the two plateaus was confirmed by Puzkiel et al., as can be seen in Figure 2.9. But upon the hydrogenation process of $2\text{Mg}:\text{Fe}$ the system only showed one equilibrium pressure [27, 37–39]

Figure 2.9: A: hydrogen absorption kinetics at 673 K and 60 bar of the Mg-Fe milled 100 h; B: desorption isotherm after hydriding [27]

Volumetric investigations under dynamic conditions of a ball-milled mixture of 2Mg:Fe in hydrogen atmosphere lead to the conclusion that the formation of Mg_2FeH_6 occurs via two consecutive steps. The formation of MgH_2 takes place at first and then the formation Mg_2FeH_6 follows [38, 44]. The reported evidences show the existence of a strong dependence of the absorption/desorption temperatures on the origin of the materials and the synthesis condition [38]. The reaction paths are clearly controlled by kinetic constraints. In fact, $\beta\text{-MgH}_2$ forms prior to Mg_2FeH_6 even though Mg_2FeH_6 is thermodynamically more stable [39]. Yet, cases where the desorption reaction appears to occur in a single step are also reported [38, 39].

In situ SR-PXD investigations performed on the system $2\text{Mg} + \text{Fe}$ under $p(\text{H}_2) = 50$ bar confirm the findings of Polanski et al.. In fact, the diffraction data shows how the formation of MgH_2 at a temperature of $\sim 215^\circ\text{C}$ precedes the formation of Mg_2FeH_6 at 350°C [44]. Here, the complete formation of Mg_2FeH_6 is constrained at low temperatures due to kinetic constraints related to the solid-solid diffusion processes [44]. It must be mentioned that, although at higher temperatures (higher than 350°C) the conversion of MgH_2 and Fe in Mg_2FeH_6 is possible, a complete formation of Mg_2FeH_6 is difficult to achieve [38, 39, 44].

Another analysis of pressure and temperature effects on the kinetics of the mix, performed by Puszkiel et al., suggests that for $T \leq 350^\circ\text{C}$ and $p \leq 44$ bar only MgH_2 , Fe and unreacted Mg are present whilst for $T > 350^\circ\text{C}$ and $p > 44$ bar Mg_2FeH_6 , MgH_2 and unreacted Fe are found [44]. This can also be seen in the phase diagram in Figure 2.10 of the Mg-Fe-H system.

Figure 2.10: Phase diagram of the Mg-Fe-H system obtained from an as-milled and hydrided 2Mg:Fe stoichiometric sample [44]

In order to provide a powerful tool to predict the best conditions to operate the systems MgH₂, Mg₂FeH₆ and MgH₂ + Mg₂FeH₆, Puszkiel *et al.* elaborated a phase diagram that takes into account both thermodynamic, as well as kinetic features. The proposed phase diagram describes the range of temperature and hydrogen pressure conditions under which the previously mentioned systems are present. One of the main results that is possible to extrapolate from this phase diagram is that the Mg-Fe-H system, at temperatures $T \leq 350^\circ\text{C}$ and hydrogen pressures $p \leq 44$ bar, can only exist as MgH₂ + Fe. However, at $T > 350^\circ\text{C}$ and $p > 44$ bar, the formation of Mg₂FeH₆ occurs and its coexistence with MgH₂ is likely.

Rzeszotarska *et al.* have investigated the Mg-Fe-H system in terms of substituting high purity iron with steel. Therefore, they used an austenitic stainless steel (316L) to synthesise Mg₂FeH₆ [45]. Their results indicated that ball milling has an effect on the crystal structure of the steel, which enables the production of martensite. After the first hour of ball milling, a drastic change in the amount of the martensite phase occurs, that increases with the ongoing milling process. The existence of martensite is necessary for the reaction between the steel with magnesium hydride. Rzeszotarska *et al.* found out that after 20 h of ball milling the ternary hydride of the Mg-Fe-H system is formed. Furthermore, the reaction between Fe and MgH₂ seems to be faster when steel is used (rather than pure Fe). This is due to the fact that Cr and Ni might enhance the reaction of Fe and MgH₂.

Moreover, Cr seems to be a substitution for Fe which leads to a change in the equilibrium pressure during desorption [45].

2.3 Scope Of Work

As presented in the previous section, the development of hydrogen storage materials is a key step for ensuring the possibility to efficiently harvest energy from renewable energy sources. Among the many storage materials investigated by the scientific community, Mg_2FeH_6 attracted particular attention in the last decades. Good gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity, as well as excellent volumetric hydrogen storage capacity, are the main advantages of the material. At the actual state of knowledge, the Mg-Fe-H system appears particularly suitable for medium temperature solar energy storage applications. This implies that its utilisation in the solar sector will require the synthesis of large quantities at a relatively low cost. Although this system is composed of relatively inexpensive elements/compounds, the possibility of replacing them with even cheaper sources of Fe and/or Mg is extremely appealing. Recently, [Rzeszotarska et al.](#) reported on the possibility of forming Mg_2FeH_6 by replacing high purity iron with commercial steel (i.e. 316L). Although the published results appear rather promising, a broader scientific effort is required. The effect of replacing pure iron with steel requires elucidation on the hydrogen storage properties of the Mg-Fe-H system. This would allow understanding of the potential of this synthesis path. In this thesis, the synthesis and characterisation of the physiochemical properties of Mg_2FeH_6 are investigated with respect to several different steels (as Fe source).

Consequently, the investigated material and characterisation techniques are presented in Chapter 3. Furthermore, the main synthesis steps, ball milling and heat treatment are explained in detail. Subsequently, the Mg-Fe-H system is investigated in form of Mg_2FeH_6 with different steels to substitute pure Fe. Chapter 4 is giving an insight into the results and discusses them with respect to the theoretical background. In the conclusion of this work, a summary of the main achievements and findings is given. At last, a brief outlook illustrates the potential of computational methods to investigate the impact of alloying elements (present in the steels) on the hydrogen storage properties.

3 Materials and Methods

In this chapter, the experimental details and characterisation techniques are presented. The first part of the chapter depicts the synthesis of the samples in terms of ball milling and annealing process, followed by a further milling step. Therefore, the corresponding experimental conditions are described in detail. In the second part of the chapter the applied characterisation techniques are introduced. In addition, the utilised experimental conditions and analytical software are also reported.

3.1 Sample Preparation

It is important to mention, that not all starting compounds used in this work are commercially available. The stainless steel powders were provided by Marek Polanski of the Military University of Warsaw, Poland. A list of the different compounds used in this work stating the respective purity in reference to a particular element in the case of the steels and Mg waste is provided in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Materials used for the synthesis

Compound	Purity	Supplier
MgH ₂	98.0 %	Alfa Aesar
Fe	99.9 %	Sigma-Aldrich
316L	63.0 % Fe	Marek Polanski
M300	65.0 % Fe	Marek Polanski

Mg₂FeH₆ was synthesised in-house following the basic steps ball milling, heat treatment and another milling step with a shaker mill (SPEX mill). The first two processing steps were performed in hydrogen atmosphere under pressure, while the last step was performed in Ar atmosphere. Due to the fact, that the utilised materials are sensitive to moisture and oxygen, they were safely handled in dedicated glove boxes under a continuously purified

Ar atmosphere (O_2 and H_2 levels ≤ 1 ppm). Additionally, the samples and materials were stored in gas-tight glass containers that are also used to carry the samples outside the glove box. This is also very important for the transfer of the samples to, e.g., DESY.

3.1.1 Ball Milling and Heat Treatment

The primary reason for using the ball milling technique in this work is to promote the formation of Mg_2FeH_6 from mixtures of MgH_2 and Fe or steels under a reactive atmosphere of hydrogen via a continuous refinement of the material particles and transfer of mechanical energy. Secondly, once the Mg_2FeH_6 is formed and underwent an annealing process, ball milling is utilised to refine the material particle size and thus improve the dehydrogenation/hydrogenation kinetic behaviour. The precise sequence of events occurring during ball milling of the mixtures of MgH_2 and Fe or steels depends mainly on the specific system and can therefore not be generalised, especially when materials with a certain degree of contamination are used [46].

During milling, repeated fracture and welding of powder particles occurring during ball-powder-ball and ball-powder-vial collisions occur. These are two basic events that ensure the continuous and intimate mixing of the compounds present in the system [30, 46, 47]. Moreover, this mechanical process leads generally to the reduction of the grain size and to the cracking of the passivating oxide layers, which are always present on metal based compounds (in particular powders). Thus, providing fresh and highly reactive new surfaces [30]. The reduced particle and grain sizes of the reactants are an important aspect of mechanically driven or supported reactions. In fact, this leads to a reduction of the distances for diffusion processes. Consequently, the diffusion barriers are minimised. Diffusion barriers hinder the completeness of many reactions occurring in solid-solid and/or solid gas state systems [46–48].

The high density of defects induced into the powder material during ball milling also contributes to the enhancement of the materials reactivity [46]. As in the case of this work, reactive ball milling (RBM) is often used to produce hydrides and is performed under hydrogen atmosphere. This procedure provides an easy way for the hydrogen to diffuse into the material and thus promoting a full conversion of the starting reactant into the final hydride system [3, 30].

Ball Milling Techniques

The five main types of ball milling techniques are displayed in Figure 3.1 [47]. In this thesis a planetary mill, as well as, a shaker mill have been utilised.

Figure 3.1: Mills for ball milling. A: planetary mill; B: vibration/shaker mill; C: attritor, also called stirring ball mill; D: pin mill; E: rolling mill [47]

Shear forces, impact forces, friction forces and compression forces are the main forces occurring during milling and have an effect on the outcome and efficiency of the milling procedure, as illustrated in Figure 3.2 [30, 47, 49, 50].

Figure 3.2: Factors on the milling procedure [30, 47, 49, 50]

The ball-to-powder ratio can vary between 1 : 1 up to 200 : 1, whereas 10 : 1 is the most common ratio, especially for SPEX mills [47]. Particularly for this work, the transferred energy plays an important role in order for the steels to go through a phase transformation from the martensite to the austenite form. Equation (3.1) describes the transfer energy P^* that is transferred from the mill to the powder during the milling process in a planetary mill

$$P^* = -\rho_b N_b m_b t (\Omega_p - \omega_v) \left[\frac{(\omega_v)^3 (r_v - \frac{d_b}{2})}{\Omega_p} + \Omega_p \omega_v R_p \right] \frac{r_v - \frac{d_b}{2}}{2\pi m_p} \quad (3.1)$$

and is the reason for the occurring defects in the material [47, 49, 50]. This process plays a key role because otherwise the reaction between iron and magnesium hydride will not take place [45]. In (3.1), ρ_b describes the degree of filling of the vial that can also be described as a yield coefficient or the interaction of the balls [49, 51]. N_b stands for the number of balls, m_b is the mass of the balls in kilograms, t the milling time in seconds and Ω_p the rotation speed of the plate in $\frac{\text{rad}}{\text{s}}$. The rotation velocity of the vial is displayed as ω_v which is also given in $\frac{\text{rad}}{\text{s}}$. The vial radius r_v , plate radius R_p and the diameter of the balls d_b are all given in meters. The mass of the material (in this case the Fe and MgH₂ powder) m_p is given in kg [49–51].

Planetary mills are the most common mills since they can be used for a diversity of applications [47]. This is due to the easy set up and cleaning for this kind of mills. In the milling process, the temperature plays an important role and occurs in pulses due to the collisions of the balls. With very high speeds of the mill the temperature and efficiency of the milling process is reduced because the balls are beginning to stick to the vial wall. Furthermore, a problem that occurs during the process is that the material is contaminated of (in most cases) Fe due to the vial and ball material. The degree of contamination is connected to the speed and duration of the milling. Therefore, a possibility to oppress the contamination is to coat the vial walls and the balls with product powder, also called seasoned milling [47]. For this work the contamination can be neglected, since the material itself contains a lot of Fe.

The main effect of milling is the decrease of the particle size down to a critical value. Any milling beyond this point will lead to deformation of the crystals, an accumulation of the energy at the surface or in the volume of crystals and a subsequent amorphisation [47]. When the particle size reduction and the particle size enlargement are at an even level the milled product is in the equilibrium state of milling. The particle size enlargement may take place due to the cold welding effects. Yet, it occurs solely after long milling processes and for certain ductile materials, as well as brittle alloys under certain conditions (e.g. time, temperature or provided energy). While the particle size is decreasing, the

effectiveness of milling is also decreasing with ongoing time and can be divided into three stages, as can be seen in Figure 3.3 [47].

Figure 3.3: Three stages of milling: Rittinger stage, aggregation stage and agglomeration stage [47]

In the first stage, the so-called Rittinger stage, the interaction of the particles can be neglected. In the second stage new surface areas are not proportional to the input energy. This is due to the particle interaction, also called aggregation. Aggregates are mechanically connected via van-der-Waals forces of magnitude $0.04 - 4 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$ [47]. The last stage is called agglomeration stage where the increase in dispersion comes to a halt and mainly mechano-chemical changes in the crystal structure occur. The particles are joined by chemical bonds of magnitude $40 - 400 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$ in this stage [47]. A rise to plastic strains and strain gradients is given by friction sliding of solids which induce structural changes in the regions that are close to the sliding interface. On top of that, the increase of a surface area fracture has an effect on the mechano-chemical processes, leading to a higher chance of contact between reactants. Therefore, on the macroscopic scale, there exists an interaction of surfaces resulting in friction. On the mesoscopic scale, the friction can be associated with wear [47].

On behalf of the fact that a system always tries to reach its minimum value of the free energy, also known as Gibbs energy, phase transformations take place during milling. The amorphisation mechanism can be described as the transformation from the crystalline to the amorphous phase. This process depends on the ability of the crystalline phase to be formed by mechanical alloying or mechanical activation to sustain a nanostructured state. The terms mechanical milling or alloying refer to a refinement of the grain size. The grain size of systems which can possibly be amorphised, are expected to be close to a critical germination size. Thus, leading to a lowering of the desorption energy which can be simultaneously connected to the desorption temperature [3, 47]. The energy difference

in the system is compensated by e.g. lattice expansion while keeping the total number of atoms constant. In multiphase nanosystems the formation of new surfaces leads to a high reactivity with different reactants [3, 47].

In order to ensure a homogeneous material and to improve the reactivity of the samples, the powder underwent a mechanical treatment in form of high energy ball milling. Therefore, two different types of milling devices were employed. As a first step of the synthesis, a Fritsch Planetary P6 was used. Here, the mechano-chemical processing was performed in hardened stainless steel milling vials with 10 mm balls and a ball to powder ratio of 30 : 1. The rotational speed was 500 rpm and the samples were milled for a duration of about 40 h. After the annealing, another milling step was performed. Therefore, a SPEX SamplePrep 8000 Mill with hardened steel milling vials was used for the final step of the synthesis. For that purpose the powders were milled for 90 minutes using hardened steel balls with a diameter of 10 mm and employing a ball to powder ratio of 10 : 1.

Heat Treatment

In order to increase the yield of formation of the ternary hydride, a heat treatment was performed. Hence, the material is exhibited to a certain temperature and pressure in hydrogen atmosphere. The time until the reaction is taking place has to be calculated beforehand. Asselli et al. performed a heat treatment at 350 °C after ball milling under hydrogen pressure of 1 bar, leading to a higher hydrogen capacity [39]. Also other researchers like Polanski et al., Rzeszotarska et al., Polanski et al., Bogdanovic et al. or Pistidda et al. use ball milling coupled with an ensuing heat treatment in order to gain a higher hydrogen capacity. There is, nevertheless, an ongoing discussion on how the process parameters, pressure and temperature are chosen [37, 38, 45, 52, 53].

In this work, autoclaves from Parr Instruments with an inner volume of 25 ml were used for all hydrogenation processes. They allow the application of pressures up to 450 bar at a temperature of 550 °C. The instrument is equipped with a manometer in order to monitor the internal pressure of the autoclave, as can be seen in Figure 3.4. For the annealing (also referred to as heat treatment), the autoclave was placed in a heater from Parr Instruments. Typically, the applied pressure is higher than the equilibrium pressure of the material in order to maximise the conversion yield.

Figure 3.4: Autoclave from Parr Instruments and the heating element

3.1.2 Synthesis of Mg_2FeH_6

As previously mentioned, the amount of energy transferred to the material during milling depends on the milling duration. Due to the fact that [Rzeszotarska et al.](#) also synthesised Mg_2FeH_6 using the stainless steel 316L before, the first step is to calculate the amount of energy transferred to the material during ball milling in their work [45]. Thereafter, the milling parameters for the synthesis in this work have to be adjusted to match their energetic values. For an experimental application of the formula, it is of interest to calculate the needed time, in order for phase changes to occur. Hence, Equation (3.1) was solved for the milling time, with the parameters listed in Table 3.2:

Table 3.2: Parameters for transfer energy calculation

Parameter	This work	Reference from [45]
ρ_b	-	-
N_b	10	10
m_b /kg	0.038	0.038
t /h	40	20
Ω_p / $\frac{rad}{s}$	52.36	68.07
$\omega_v = -1.25 \Omega_p$ / $\frac{rad}{s}$	-65.45	-85.09
r_v /m	0.0375	0.0345
R_p /m	0.0608	0.0700
d_b /m	0.01	0.01
m_p /kg	0.0025	0.0025

leading to the following estimated milling time

$$t^* = \frac{N_{br} m_{br} t_p (\Omega_{pr} - \omega_{vr}) \left[\frac{(\omega_{vr})^3 (r_{vr} - \frac{d_b}{2})}{\Omega_{pr}} + \Omega_{pr} \omega_{vr} R_{pr} \right] (r_{vr} - \frac{d_b}{2})}{N_{b*} m_{b*} (\Omega_{p*} - \omega_{v*}) \left[\frac{(\omega_{v*})^3 (r_{v*} - \frac{d_b}{2})}{\Omega_{p*}} + \Omega_{p*} \omega_{v*} R_{p*} \right] (r_{v*} - \frac{d_b}{2})} = 41.4764 \text{ h} \quad (3.2)$$

with r in the indices for the parameters from the reference and $*$ for the parameters used for this work. It is noteworthy, that the needed milling time t^* can be reduced when the parameters or milling devices are changed.

For the heat treatment the pressure p at RT has to be calculated with the ideal gas law (3.3), in order to obtain the needed pressure at the hydrogenation temperature.

$$p \cdot V = n \cdot R \cdot T \quad (3.3)$$

using the volume V , mole mass n , ideal gas constant R and temperature T . The process was carried out under a pressure of about 150 bar and 450 °C for about 13 h, in order to make sure that the material was fully hydrogenated. Subsequently, in order to get a more nano-crystalline material, another milling process was applied, i.e. SPEX milling (shaker mill).

3.1.3 Considered Substitution of Pure Fe in Form of the Stainless Steels 316L and M300

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the focus of this work is to investigate the possibility of using cost-effective materials as possible hydrogen storage systems. Thus, the stainless steels M300 and 316L are investigated as two alternatives for pure iron powder.

316L

The composition of the stainless steel 316L is displayed in Table 3.3 [54]. Due to its low carbon content, this material is used in various applications and is advantageous especially for piping since it is corrosion-resistant. 316L belongs to the austenitic stainless steels and provides therefore a face centered cubic crystal structure [54]. The synthesis was prepared analogously to Rzeszotarska et al. using the same stoichiometric ratio of 2Mg:Fe.

Table 3.3: Composition of 316L and M300; according to [54, 55]

Element	316L		M300	
	Min /%	Max /%	Min /%	Max /%
Fe				
Ni	10	13	18	19
Cr	16.5	18.5		
Co			8.5	9.5
Mo	2	2.5	4.7	5.2
Ti			0.5	0.8
Al			0.05	0.15
Si		1		0.1
Mn		2		0.1
C		0.030		0.03
P		0.045		0.01
S		0.015		0.01
N		0.1		

M300

M300 belongs to the group of maraging steels, which are steels that possess properties between martensitic and aging steels [56]. This steel possesses the characteristic martensitic crystal structure (body-centered tetragonal form of iron). The main advantages of

this alloy are the high strength and hardness, which are derived through precipitation of intermetallic compounds. Yet, it is noteworthy, that strength is not contributed by carbon, since the alloy is low in carbon [56]. The powder contains spherical particles with diameters in the range of 10 – 45 μm with a spherical shape [55].

3.1.4 Considered Substitution of Pure MgH_2

Previous works from [Passing](#) have shown, that pure Mg can be substituted by Mg waste [57].

Preparation of Mg Waste

An attempt to synthesise Mg_2FeH_6 using Mg-based wastes as the source of Mg was made using wastes provided by the in-house workshop of the Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht. In order to achieve a high yield of conversion of the waste material into MgH_2 , the received material underwent an initial treatment for reducing the material particle size. Thus, increasing its reactivity towards hydrogen. Consequently, the as received material, which was provided in form of shavings and chips of the size of several millimetres, was milled using a rotary high energy ball mill (Simoloyer-CM08 of the company ZOZ GmbH) under Ar atmosphere with a ball to powder ratio of 1 : 20 [57–59]. The milling velocities varied between 700 rpm for half a minute and 300 rpm for the other half during a total milling time of two hours [57, 59]. The final step to prepare the Mg powder from the waste material is the sieving. In order to obtain a powder with a particle size of 63 μm (chosen according to the ISO 565 R20/3 standard) the Mg waste was sieved for one hour with an amplitude of 2 mm in a sieving machine from Fritsch (Analysette 3 Pro) [60]. The composition of the waste material is given in Table 3.4 and resembles closely the die casting alloy AZ91. Since 90% of magnesium alloys are being processed via die casting, using an alloy similar to AZ91 is a reasonable choice [61].

Table 3.4: Composition of AZ91 and the used Mg waste

Element	AZ 91		Mg waste
	Min /%	Max /%	Weight -%
Mg	90.000		76.090
Al	8.300	9.700	13.600
Zn	0.350	1.000	8.600
Mn	0.150	0.500	0.130
Si		0.100	
Cu		0.030	0.130
Fe		0.005	
Ni		0.002	
C		0.030	
P		0.010	
S		0.010	
Ca			0.060
Nd			0.450
Y			0.240
Ag			0.700

Although the material was exposed to an ambient atmosphere for several weeks before being utilised in this work, only small traces of MgO can be detected in the sample. In the later process, as for all the other materials investigated in this work, the handling, characterisation and further investigations were performed under a continuously purified Ar atmosphere.

Synthesis of Magnesium Hydride from Mg Waste

In order to synthesise MgH_2 , the milled Mg waste was used. For the hydrogenation solely the second step, heat treatment without prior ball milling, was performed. A comparison of the diffraction patterns of the annealed and the purchased MgH_2 material can be seen in Figure 3.5.

Since the emphasis of this work lies on the substitution of pure Fe further investigations have not been performed for samples synthesised with Mg waste.

Figure 3.5: MgH₂ as purchased and as prepared from waste material

3.2 Characterisation Techniques

The characterisation of the investigated material was performed using several different techniques. These techniques are briefly explained in the following section. Furthermore, general information about the experimental conditions are provided.

3.2.1 X-Ray Diffraction

The samples were investigated by X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) which is a non-destructive technique and usually the first method to determine the composition of a crystalline material [62, 63]. The quick identification of the phases, determination of the crystallite size and strain, based on XRD data is possible. Nevertheless, determination of the structure and composition, which is performed by fitting the acquired diffraction patterns via the Rietveld method, requires longer evaluation times. From the physical point of view the X-ray diffraction is the coherent (in-phase) elastic scattering of the incident X-ray beam, from a periodical lattice, that occurs under certain angular conditions. The relationship between the incident monochromatic X-ray beam and a periodic 3D lattice is well described by the so called Bragg's law:

$$n \cdot \lambda = 2 \cdot d_{hkl} \cdot \sin(\theta) \quad (3.4)$$

n is an integer value, λ is the wavelength of the incident X-ray beam, d is the interplanar distance and θ is the exit angle with respect to the diffraction planes equal to the angle θ of incidence (Figure 3.6) [62, 63]. In a common laboratory diffractometer the X-rays are generated in a X-ray tube operating under high-voltage in vacuum. [62, 63]. Within a X-ray tube there are a cathode and an anode. At the cathode, which is normally made of tungsten, some electrons are expelled via the thermoionic effect. Due to the large potential difference, existing between the cathode and the anode, the electrons generated at the cathode are projected (and accelerated) toward the anode. While approaching the anode, the electrons start to experience the repulsive interaction arising from the electronic clouds of the anode atoms. This leads to the deviation of the electrons from their trajectory. Furthermore, an inevitable loss of energy can be detected that appears in the form of photons with a broad and continuous energy distribution. This continuous radiation is also called Bremsstrahlung. When increasing the energy of the incident X-rays (by increasing the difference of potential between the cathode and the anode) the energy distribution of the generated photons increases (shorter wavelengths). When the difference of the applied potential is high enough, the electrons possess sufficient energy to remove some electrons from the inner core of the anode atoms and the so called characteristic radiation, $K\alpha$, is generated. This radiation has a specific energy value, which depends on the anode material. The characteristic radiation is usually separated from the Bremsstrahlung radiation by using specific filter (e.g. pyrolyzed graphite). Thus, a highly monochromatic beam is produced and directed to the sample [62, 63].

Figure 3.6: Principle of Bragg's Law [64]

For the investigation of the crystalline phases that are present in the starting reactants or that form during the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation processes, *ex situ* as well as *in situ* XRD were performed on the investigated materials.

***Ex Situ* XRD**

Ex situ powder X-ray diffraction (PXD) was used throughout this thesis to investigate the composition of the investigated materials. At HZG the *ex situ* measurements are performed with a Bruker D8 Discover device with a Bragg-Brentano geometry, operating at 50 kV and 1000 mA. The used X-Ray source is copper $K\alpha$ (Cu with wavelength $\lambda = 1.541854 \text{ \AA}$) and the detector used for the measurements is the VANTEC general detector from Bruker. For the experiments the diffractograms were acquired with an exposure time of 400 s and an angular range 2θ of $10^\circ - 90^\circ$ with a step size of $\Delta 2\theta = 16^\circ$. In order to prevent samples from oxidation, a sample holder that is sealed with an Ar filled poly-methyl-methacrylate (PMMA) dome was employed during the measurements. The scattering of the PMMA dome creates a bump in the final diffraction pattern, which later on can be subtracted. The base of the sample holder consists of a Si substrate. With the software DIFFRAC.EVA and the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) the collected data can be evaluated in terms of the phase composition.

***In Situ* XRD**

In situ Synchrotron-Radiation Powder X-Ray Diffraction (SR-PXD) experiments, which are conducted with high intensity monochromatic beams, are a powerful approach to determine the temperature- and time-dependent evolution of crystalline phases and the sequences of chemical reactions. Furthermore, owing to a pattern acquisition time of few seconds, reaction pathways, phase transformations and structural changes can be investigated using this technique.

The diffraction patterns were acquired at Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) at the facility PETRA III at the P02.1 powder diffraction and total scattering beamline. The acquisition of the diffraction patterns are done in a Debye-Scherrer geometry. At PETRA III the diffraction patterns were collected using a Perkin Elmer XRD 1621 detector with a 2048 x 2048 pixel array and a pixel size of (200 x 200) μm . Since there was a change in the set-up between measurements, acquisitions were performed under two different wavelengths, at $\lambda = 0.20757 \text{ \AA}$ and $\lambda = 0.20761 \text{ \AA}$ respectively. In Figure 3.7, a cell for the *in situ* measurements is displayed.

This special setup allows to record the sample temperature and gas pressure [65]. Measurements can be performed in the pressure range 0.01 – 200 bar. The samples were filled into a sapphire capillary with an outer diameter of 1 mm and an inner diameter of 0.6 mm. The capillaries were fixed with Fe ferrules at the end and were then mounted

Figure 3.7: Cell for *in situ* measurements with the sapphire capillary

in the sample holder with gas-tight Swagelok connections. Underneath the capillary, an electrical heating block is located, which is operated by a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller. When the capillary is placed in the sample holder, a thermocouple reaches in the capillary with its tip almost in contact with the sample. This allows to monitor and measure the temperature during the acquisitions of diffraction patterns. The samples were heated from RT to 400 °C with a heating rate of $5 \frac{\text{K}}{\text{min}}$. Every 10 seconds a two-dimensional SR-PXD pattern was collected. In order to ensure proper evacuation, as well, as a steady pressure during the experiments, a pressure transducer connected to the sample holder was employed. All measurements of this work were conducted in hydrogen atmosphere with a pressure of 100 bar for the absorption and against static vacuum for the desorption. Furthermore, the samples investigated in the absorption process were desorbed prior to the experiments at HZG.

LaB₆ powder was used to determine the X-ray wavelength and the instrumental broadening precisely. The obtained two-dimensional images were carefully masked to exclude single crystal diffraction spots, e.g. from the sapphire capillary. Afterwards they were

radially integrated to one-dimensional conventional diffractograms by means of the program FIT2D [66]. Subsequently, all diffractograms collected in the experiments were combined to a two-dimensional (temperature vs. q-vector) colour-coded intensity map using the software Origin [67]. The structure models of the known phases were found in the ICSD.

3.2.2 Volumetric Measurement

In order to characterise the amount of hydrogen absorbed/desorbed by the synthesised material, an in-house built Sieverts type apparatus was utilised. Using this machine, measurements can be performed in a range of 0.01-100 bar and at temperatures up to 500°C. Inside the machine, there is, next to the sample volume, an equal separate volume also called reference volume. The two volumes are connected via a differential pressure gauge. Therefore, all temperature-induced pressure changes are compensated and only differences due to hydrogen absorption or desorption processes are recorded. The pressure changes are subsequently converted into the change of the gravimetric hydrogen content of the investigated samples. This can be done by applying the van der Waals equation of state, see Equation (3.5), which is derived from the ideal gas law [68].

$$(P + a(\frac{n}{V})^2)(\frac{V}{n} - b) = RT \quad (3.5)$$

P is the pressure, a and b are characteristic constants for the gas, where a is a correction for the intermolecular forces and b a correction for the finite molecular size. For hydrogen $a = 2.45 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ Pa m}^3$ and $b = 26.61 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{mol}}$. V is the volume, R is the gas constant, T the temperature and n the mole mass [68].

For the experiments, an amount of 150 – 250 mg of the sample was loaded into the sample holder in an Ar filled glove box with O₂ and H₂O levels ≤ 1 ppm. The hydrogen used in the experiments had a purity of 99.999%. The samples were heated from RT with rates or 5 $\frac{\text{K}}{\text{min}}$. The obtained kinetic curves not only allow measuring the amount of hydrogen absorbed/desorbed by the investigated material, but also understanding the reaction mechanisms involved in the processes. In this regard, a powerful tool for the kinetic modelling is the employment of the fitting of application of gas-solid models. This models were originally developed for phase transformations of solid materials and then extrapolated into gas-solid reactions [69, 70]. Among one of the method to apply the gas-solid models, it is possible to find the reduced time method or so-called Sharps and Jones

method [71, 72]. The idea is to identify a kinetic model to represent the rate-limiting step in a gas-solid reaction. In this method, experimental data (in form of gravimetric capacity over time) is expressed as

$$F(\alpha) = K\left(\frac{t}{t_{0.5}}\right) \quad (3.6)$$

with the rate constant (k). The $\frac{t}{t_{0.5}}$ is the time where the reaction is at fraction $\alpha = 0.5$. The fraction consists of the hydrogen capacity over the maximum reached capacity for each sample. In order to find the best fitting model, several plots of the theoretical ($\frac{t}{t_{0.5}}$) versus the experimental ($\frac{t}{t_{0.5}}$) data are plotted. In this work, the models have been applied to the fraction of the whole capacity of the dehydrogenation curve between 0.1 and 0.8. The implemented rate equations of the different models are listed in Table 3.5. The best fitting reaction rate model can be determined, when the slope of the fitted line is closest to 1, the intercept is closest to 0 and the squared error is closest to 1.

In Table 3.5, the values for the different models are displayed [73].

Table 3.5: Solid state rate expression for different reaction models; according to [71–73]

Model		Differential Form $f(\alpha) = \frac{1}{k} \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$	Integral form $g(\alpha) = kt$
Diffusion models	1-D diffusion (D1)	$\frac{1}{2\alpha}$	α^2
	2-D diffusion (D2)	$1 - \left(\frac{1}{\ln(1-\alpha)}\right)$	$((1 - \alpha)\ln(1 - \alpha)) + \alpha$
	3-D Jander equation (D3)	$\frac{3(1-\alpha)^{\frac{2}{3}}}{2(1-(1-\alpha)^{\frac{1}{3}})}$	$(1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{3}})^2$
	Ginstling-Brounshtein (D4)	$\frac{3}{2((1-\alpha)^{\frac{-1}{3}}-1)}$	$1 - \left(\frac{2\alpha}{3}\right) - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{2}{3}}$
Reaction order models	First order (F1)	$(1 - \alpha)$	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)$
	Second order (F2)	$(1 - \alpha)^2$	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}$
	Third order (F3)	$(1 - \alpha)^3$	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{3}}$
	Fourth order (F4)	$(1 - \alpha)^4$	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
	Fifth order (F5)	$(1 - \alpha)^5$	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{2}{5}}$
Geometric models	Contracting area (R2)	$2(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}$
	Contracting volume (R3)	$3(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{2}{3}}$	$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{3}}$

Another method for performing volumetric measurements is the utilisation of an apparatus that employs the absolute pressure principle. One of the most common volumetric machines found in the laboratories using the absolute pressure principle is the PCTPro 2000. In this machine, roughly 500 mg of material was used per measurement. More-

over, it was transferred in a sample vial made of steel which is closed with a screw-cap including a porous sintered metal filter. The sample vial was placed in a sample holder and in order to reduce the total volume of the sample holder, a dead volume, in form of steel cylinders was added. Thus, the precision of the measurement can be increased, because the effects of the gas phase, i.e. temperature, are reduced. This is important, since in the calibration and application of pressures different reference volumes have to be applied. The experiments were conducted with a heating rate of $10 \frac{\text{K}}{\text{min}}$ from RT to the experimental temperature. All measurements were carried out in hydrogen atmosphere under pressures ranging between 85 and 90 bar. The combination and comparison of the results obtained from the two different volumetric methods provide a useful tool to verify observed phenomena and results.

3.2.3 FTIR

The Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is used to acquire information on the chemical bonds and functional groups present in the investigated material [74]. Basically, the absorption of the applied infrared beam is measured and displayed as transmittance (or absorbance) versus wave number. Compared to ultra-violet visible light, infrared light is at higher wavelength but lower energy. In order to utilise this technique, the chemical bonds present in the investigated material must display a dipolar nature. The identification of the different functional groups is possible, since the natural vibration frequency is characteristic for each group [74]. When infrared radiation hits a material, different vibration modes are activated. The measured wave numbers typically lay between $4000 - 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and represent the frequency of the modes. A FTIR spectrometer usually consists of an interferometer, a light source (infrared), a sample compartment, a detector, an amplifier and a computer. The generated radiation hits the sample and reaches the detector in the end. The amplifier and an analogue-to-digital converter, amplify and afterwards convert the signal to a digital signal, also called interferogram. In the end, the signal can be translated to a spectrum with the Fast-Fourier-Transformation (FFT). An example for a transformed signal can be seen in Figure 3.8 [74].

Figure 3.8: Example for a Fourier transform of an interferogram to produce a single-beam spectrum [74]

The characterisation of the material were carried out with an Agilent Technologies Cary 630 FT-IR located in an Ar filled glove box with O₂ and H₂O levels ≤ 1 ppm. Each measurement is acquired in the transmission mode in a spectral range of 4000 – 650 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

3.2.4 Differential Thermal Analyses and Mass Spectroscopy

The Differential Thermal Analyses (DTA) is a characterisation technique with which the difference in the temperature between a reference and a sample is measured during a thermal program (e.g. heating, cooling or thermal cycles) [75]. The temperature difference between the reference and the sample is associated to phenomena occurring at the sample side (e.g. melting, crystallisation, decomposition etc.) Thus, the electrical signal generated by the temperature gradient is translated in an energy value. Therefore, starting temperature, heating rate (for heating and cooling), maximum temperature and, if desired, the time for the isothermal process have to be defined. In the case of this work, the DTA device was allowed acquiring also thermogravimetric information (TGA). The gases evolving from the investigated samples during the DTA measurements were analysed by a mass spectrometer (MS). Prior to measuring the material, a base line measurement with an empty crucible should be performed. Out of the DTA curve, the activation energy (for the hydrogenation) can be derived using the Kissinger Equation (3.7) [75].

$$\left(\ln \frac{\beta}{T_p^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{A R}{E_a}\right) - \frac{E_a}{R T_p} \quad [76] \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.9: DTA measuring system where the crucibles are standing free [75]

In the formula the T_p is the peak temperature, which corresponds to the heating rate β . Additionally, E_a is the activation energy, A describes a pre-exponential factor and the R is the gas constant [76].

For the investigation of the thermal behaviour during dehydrogenation reactions, a Netzsch STA 409 C combined with a Hiden Analytical HAL 201 Mass-Spectrometer was used. This device is located inside an Ar filled glove box with O_2 and H_2O levels ≤ 1 ppm. For the DTA-MS measurements about 1 – 2 mg were used whereas for the DTA measurements about 25 mg of sample were used in order to obtain a better signal to noise ratio. The samples were placed in an Al_2O_3 crucible and heated up to the desired temperature. Measurements were performed under a constant flow of Ar of $50 \frac{ml}{min}$. The peak temperatures can be determined from the experimental DTA curves and after plotting $\ln(\frac{\beta}{T_p^2})$ over $\frac{1}{T_p}$ the activation energy can be calculated. This procedure is possible due to the fact, that the slope is represented by $\frac{-E_a}{R}$.

4 Results

In this chapter, which is divided into three sections, the most important experimental results obtained in the investigation of the samples are presented. The first Section 4.1 presents the results obtained for the pure system, the second Section 4.2 presents the results obtained for the system synthesised with 316L and the last Section 4.3 entails the results for the system prepared with M300.

4.1 Reference System

This section begins with the results of the characterisation of the pristine (synthesised starting from highly pure Mg and Fe) Mg_2FeH_6 . This allows to evaluate the systems synthesised with the waste materials accurately. Furthermore, the variation of the different systems can be highlighted as a function of the Fe source.

4.1.1 *Ex Situ* PXD

PXD measurements were performed in order to identify the crystalline phases that are present after the synthesis. The result of this investigation is reported in Figure 4.1. For an easy assignment of the diffraction peaks of the sample after the final preparation step, the diffraction patterns of pure Fe and MgH_2 were included.

Figure 4.1: XRD of reference sample (Mg_2FeH_6); as prepared

The main Bragg peaks present in the diffraction pattern of the synthesised material reveal the presence of Mg_2FeH_6 . This result indicates that the synthesis was successful. Besides the peaks for Mg_2FeH_6 , less intense and broader diffraction peaks belonging to MgH_2 are also visible. Interestingly, no evidence for unreacted Fe is detected.

In Figure 4.2, the PXD pattern for all of the samples after the first desorption is displayed. In all of the samples Bragg peaks for Mg and Fe are visible. Hence, all of them decomposed.

Figure 4.2: XRD of the samples after the first desorption

4.1.2 DTA-MS and Activation Energy

In Figure 4.3 the MS-coupled DTA analyses for the prepared pristine sample are displayed. The y-axis on the right hand side shows the amount of gas that is released upon heating and the left hand side y-axis shows the intensity of the thermal event. The MS analyses provide information about the gases evolving from the sample upon heat treatment. For this work, H_2 (hydrogen), CH_4 (methane) and C_2H_6 (ethane) were monitored upon heating, with a heating rate of $10 \frac{K}{min}$. The obtained result of the DTA curve indicates the presence of an endothermic event starting at about $250^\circ C$ and having the peak maximum at about $345^\circ C$. According to the MS analyses the endothermic signal is associated with the release of hydrogen, thus indicating the decomposition of the hydride phases Mg_2FeH_6 and of MgH_2 .

Figure 4.3: DTA and MS traces of the reference system (Mg_2FeH_6) as prepared; heating to 450 °C with a heating rate of $10 \frac{\text{K}}{\text{min}}$ and $50 \frac{\text{ml}}{\text{min}}$ Ar flow

Calculation of the activation energy gives an insight about the amount of energy that is required to be transferred to the material for a dehydrogenation. Therefore, the peak maxima of the main thermal events for DTA curves acquired with different heating rates are identified (see Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: DTA curves for the reference system (Mg_2FeH_6) with different heating rates

The activation energy can then be calculated employing the Kissinger method [76]. In Figure 4.5 and Table 4.1 the Kissinger plot and the according results of the linear fitting are displayed. The activation energy for the reference system is $100 \pm 6 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$.

Figure 4.5: Activation energy for the reference system (Mg_2FeH_6)

Table 4.1: Results from the linear fitting of the reference system (Mg_2FeH_6)

Equation	$y=a+b \cdot x$
Plot	$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{(T_{\max})^2}\right)$
Weight	no weighting
Intercept	8.30363 ± 1.25023
Slope	$-12053.39513 \pm 754.13398$
Adj.R-square	0.98452
R-Square	0.98839
Peasons R	-0.99418
Residual Sum of Squares	0.02952

4.1.3 Volumetric Measurements

In Figure 4.6, the desorption curves recorded over cycling at 450°C against a static vacuum (initial value 10^{-2} bar) are displayed. The fitting of the curves can be found in Appendix A.1. Since the absorption kinetic behaviour is too fast to measure correct values, only the desorption curves are shown. The onset temperature for dehydrogenation is approximately 320°C . The values of measured gravimetric capacity, as displayed in Figure 4.7, appear to suggest a small decrease of the storage capacity. The slight drop in the capacity occurs after the 1st cycle and from the 8th cycle onward. After the first desorption, the capacity of the system is 4.78 wt% which drops to 4.16 wt% after the last cycle. The dehydrogenation is completed in roughly 6 min and after around 3 min 80 % of the dehydrogenation is complete.

Figure 4.6: Desorption curves over cycling of reference (Mg_2FeH_6)

Figure 4.7: Gravimetric capacity over cycling of the reference (Mg_2FeH_6)

The diffraction patterns after the 10th cycle are shown in Figure 4.8. Compared with the diffraction patterns of the starting material (shown in Figure 4.1), it is visible, that in the cycled material a higher amount of MgH_2 is present. Peaks at 28° , 35.8° and 54.7° are more intense than the as-prepared sample. This fact can be ascribed to segregation phenomena occurring upon cycling.

Figure 4.8: XRD of the reference (Mg_2FeH_6) after 10 cycles; absorbed state

4.1.4 *In Situ* PXD

In order to understand the processes taking place upon hydrogen absorption and desorption of the reference sample, the evolution of the crystalline phases are studied by *in situ* SR-PXD. The SR-PXD analysis of the absorption process is displayed in Figure 4.9. The starting phases at RT are Fe, Mg and also MgH_2 which is in good agreement with the *ex situ* XRD displayed in Figure 4.1. Upon heating, at around 370°C the ternary hydride forms. The hydrogenation is occurring in one step, without MgH_2 as precursor. As seen in Figure 4.9, the intensity of the MgH_2 peaks is constant over the overall length of the measurement. This indicates that the MgH_2 utilised for the formation of Mg_2FeH_6 is the one obtained by the hydrogenation of the starting free Mg. In addition, due to the lack of intensity variation of the already present MgH_2 diffraction peaks (which was checked in 3D plots; not displayed here), it becomes clear that the just formed MgH_2 reacts with the available Fe to form Mg_2FeH_6 .

Figure 4.9: *In situ* SR-PXD; absorption at 400 °C and 100 bar; reference (Mg_2FeH_6)

The SR-PXD pattern (Figure 4.10) for the desorption process was acquired during heating from RT to 400 °C under static vacuum. It reveals that, as seen in the *ex situ* PXD of Figure 4.1, the starting material contains mostly Mg_2FeH_6 plus a small amount of MgH_2 . Upon heating at about 280 °C, MgH_2 decomposes and free Mg is formed. This event is followed later by the decomposition of Mg_2FeH_6 at about 320 °C and the formation of additional Mg and Fe. No remnant ternary hydride is left after the isothermal period at 400 °C.

Figure 4.10: *In situ* XRD; desorption at 400 °C and static vacuum of the reference (Mg_2FeH_6)

4.1.5 Room Temperature Absorption

As the experiments were performed at RT and 85 bar in the Sieverts apparatus (both for differential and absolute method), an absorption was visible. Since *ex situ* PXD measurements did not show a formation of Mg_2FeH_6 (diffraction patterns not reported in this thesis) a DTA-MS measurement was performed, which is displayed in Figure 4.11. There is a clear first and second peak visible. The first peak can be attributed to MgH_2 , whereas the second peak is due to the desorption of Mg_2FeH_6 . Moreover, not only hydrogen, but also some ethane seems to be desorbing from the sample. Yet, this can be attributed to a bad signal to noise ratio, since only a small amount of sample is investigated. Furthermore, there is no clear peak visible, as for hydrogen, and if compared with Figure 4.3 the intensity of the signal is five times higher. Consequently, the signal to noise ratio in this measurement tends to be worse and fluctuations are more striking.

Figure 4.11: DTA after cycling and subsequent RT absorption at 85 bar; reference (Mg_2FeH_6)

4.2 316L

4.2.1 *Ex Situ* PXD

In Figure 4.12 the PXD of the system synthesised with 316L instead of pure Fe is displayed. It is visible that Mg_2FeH_6 was synthesised successfully. Nevertheless, there is some remnant Fe present and another phase which cannot be identified clearly. Due to the fact that in 316L the main alloying elements are Cr, Ni and Mo (compare Table 3.3) it is likely that it is a phase composed of Fe, Cr, Ni and Mo. Compared to the PXD of the reference system (see Figure 4.1), it appears as if no remnant MgH_2 is present.

Figure 4.12: XRD of the 316L system

4.2.2 DTA-MS and Activation Energy

In Figure 4.13 the DTA and MS analyses for the as-prepared sample synthesised with the steel 316L are displayed. The obtained result indicates the presence of an endothermic event starting at about 225°C and having the peak maximum at about 325°C. In the DTA curve there is a slight shoulder visible, which can be assigned to the desorption of MgH_2 prior to Mg_2FeH_6 . As expected, the MS analyses confirms that the endothermic signal is associated with the release of hydrogen. This indicates the decomposition of the hydride phases Mg_2FeH_6 and of MgH_2 .

Figure 4.13: DTA and MS traces of the 316L system; as prepared

In Figure 4.14 the DTA curves for the different heating rates are displayed. There is, as seen before in the DTA-MS curve in Figure 4.13, a visible shoulder part. Yet, for the calculation of the activation energy the main peak was taken into account.

Figure 4.14: DTA curves for the 316L system with different heating rates

For the calculation of the activation energy the Kissinger method was applied. The corresponding plot is displayed in Figure 4.15, with the results of the fitting in Table 4.2.

The activation energy for the 316L is about $87 \pm 7 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$. Compared to the reference sample the activation energy of the 316L sample is $13 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$ lower.

Figure 4.15: Activation energy for the 316L system

Table 4.2: Results from the linear fitting of the system with 316L

Equation	$y=a+b \cdot x$
Plot	$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{(T_{\max})^2}\right)$
Weight	no weighting
Intercept	6.82818 ± 1.36237
Slope	$-10514.97166 \pm 778.53948$
Adj. R-square	0.97843
R-Square	0.98382
Peasons R	-0.99188
Residual Sum of Squares	0.045054

4.2.3 Volumetric Measurements

Due to technical issues with the machine no complete cycling could be performed for this sample. Nevertheless, the first four hydrogen desorption curves were acquired (Figure 4.16). The obtained capacity in the 1st cycle is at 2.6 wt% and decreases to about 2.2 wt% in the 4th cycle. In this sample, there is a visible decrease over cycling. In terms of speed, the sample synthesised with 316L shows faster kinetics than the reference. After about 4 min the sample is fully dehydrogenated, whereas in the reference about 2 min

more are necessary. However, more cycles are required in order to make a clear statement. Furthermore, a different machine was used (due to technical issues) which can lead to slightly different experimental parameters.

Figure 4.16: Desorption curves over cycling of the 316L system

4.2.4 *In Situ* PXD

The investigation of the hydrogen absorption of the 316L sample was conducted in the same way as for the reference sample. The Bragg reflections, as displayed in Figure 4.17, of Fe and Mg are visible in the diffraction pattern of the starting material. This observation is in good agreement with the obtained *ex situ* PXD (see Figure 4.12). Furthermore, the presence of Fe after the absorption can also be observed, as previously seen in the *ex situ* PXD. However, due to the broadness of the observed diffraction peaks, we cannot exclude the presence of Mg_2Ni , marked with a question mark. Upon heating, at around 210°C the diffraction peaks of Mg_2FeH_6 and of MgH_2 start to appear. The intensity of these peaks increases with increasing temperature.

Figure 4.17: *In-situ* SR-PXD; absorption at 400 °C and 100 bar; 316L

The desorption of the system is displayed in Figure 4.18. Upon heating, at around 330 °C Mg_2FeH_6 starts to decompose into Mg and Fe and again the weak peaks which were previously attributed to the possible presence of Mg_2Ni are visible. The desorption seems to be taking place in a single step.

Figure 4.18: *In situ* SR-PXD; desorption at 400 °C and 100 bar; 316L

4.2.5 Room Temperature Absorption

The DTA-MS analysis of the sample after cycling and subsequent RT absorption under a pressure of 85 bar are shown in Figure 4.19. In this sample the phenomenon of two endothermic peaks is clearly visible. Moreover, prior to the two main peaks, there appears to be an additional endothermic signal beginning at around 150 °C and ending at around 175 °C. The main event starts afterwards and has maximum peak temperatures at 240 °C and 285 °C, respectively.

Figure 4.19: DTA after cycling and subsequent RT absorption at 85 bar; 316L

4.3 M300

4.3.1 *Ex Situ* PXD

The following Figure 4.20 shows the diffraction patterns of the as-prepared sample with M300. The synthesis procedure is the same as described for the reference material. Mg_2FeH_6 was synthesised successfully. Nevertheless, there is some remnant Fe, or another phase, present. Due to the fact, that in M300 the main alloying elements are Ni, Co and Mo (compare Table 3.3) it is likely that this phase contains these elements. Since different phases may present overlapping diffraction peaks, a clear attribution of this peak is not possible. Compared to the PXD pattern of the reference system (Figure 4.1), signals ascribable to highly crystalline MgH_2 are visible in this analysis. However, the presence of MgH_2 in highly nanostructured form cannot be excluded.

Figure 4.20: XRD of M300 as prepared

4.3.2 DTA-MS and Activation Energy

DTA and MS analyses for the as-prepared material with M300 are displayed in Figure 4.21. The obtained result indicates the presence of an endothermic event having onset temperature at about 200°C and peak maximum at about 300°C. According to the MS analyses the endothermic signal is associated with the release of hydrogen. This indicates the decomposition of Mg₂FeH₆ and, if present, of MgH₂.

Figure 4.21: DTA-MS of M300

In Figure 4.22 the DTA curves for the different heating rates are displayed.

Figure 4.22: DTA curves for M300 for different heating rates

The linear fitting of the Kissinger plot with the results for the activation energy calculation is depicted in Figure 4.23 and Table 4.3. The resulting value for the activation energy is

$115 \pm 3 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$. Therefore, this sample requires the highest activation energy of all the three investigated systems.

Figure 4.23: Activation energy for M300

Table 4.3: Results from the linear fitting of the system with M300

Equation	$y=a+b \cdot x$
Plot	$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{(T_{\max})^2}\right)$
Weight	no weighting
Intercept	13.18337 ± 0.62053
Slope	$-13928.32021 \pm 349.59079$
Adj. R-square	0.99748
R-Square	0.99811
Peasons R	-0.99906
Residual Sum of Squares	0.00496

4.3.3 Volumetric Measurements

In Figure 4.25 the desorption curves recorded over cycling at 450°C are illustrated. The desorption was performed against a static vacuum (initial value 10^{-2} bar). The fitting of the curves can be found in the Appendix A.2. The onset temperature for dehydrogenation is approximately 320°C .

Figure 4.24: Desorption curves over cycling of M300

The values of measured gravimetric capacity, displayed in Figure 4.25, indicate that the material's hydrogen storage capacity remains almost constant during the overall cycling period. After the first desorption, the capacity of the system is 2.78 wt%, which drops to 2.52 wt% after the last cycle. The dehydrogenation is completed in roughly 3 min. Furthermore, after around 1 min 80 % of the dehydrogenation is complete.

Figure 4.25: Gravimetric capacity over cycling of M300

4.3.4 *In Situ* PXD

As can be seen in the SR-PXD (Figure 4.26), the absorption does not clearly seem to take place in the sample prepared from M300. There are several possible reasons for the reaction not taking place. The most reasonable is that due to a technical issue the hydrogen could not completely reach the sample cell. Consequently, the SR-PXD analysis was carried out under a hydrogen pressure lower than the intended one. Nevertheless, upon heating the Mg peaks disappear and peaks for MgH_2 appear. At around 330°C the peaks for MgH_2 disappear again.

Figure 4.26: *In situ* SR-PXD; absorption at 400 °C and 100 bar; M300

As already noticed in the sample prepared from 316L (Figure 4.17), besides the formation of free Mg, the formation of Mg_2Ni is also visible during the desorption process. Which is in good agreement with the composition of the steels, depicted in Table 3.3. For 316L and M300, Ni is one of the major alloying elements with over 10% and 18%, respectively. Furthermore, the decomposition of Mg_2FH_6 into Mg and Fe starts at a temperature of about 315 °C.

Figure 4.27: *In situ* XRD; desorption at 400 °C and 100 bar; M300

4.3.5 Room Temperature Absorption

The DTA analysis performed on the material, cycled and hydrogenated at room temperature at 85 bar, is displayed in Figure 4.28. There is a clear small endothermic signal that precedes the main endothermic peak as it has already been observed for the reference and the 316L sample, as shown in Figure 4.11 and Figure 4.19, respectively. The onset temperature for the smaller signal is at about 140 °C. Due to the overlapping of the two signals it is not possible to clearly state the onset temperature of the main signal, which has its peak maximum at 248 °C. The associated MS analysis confirms that the two signals are associated to the release of hydrogen from the sample.

Figure 4.28: DTA after cycling and subsequent RT absorption at 85 bar; M300

The results reported in this thesis clearly indicate that pure Fe can be replaced. Several different types of steels can act as Fe source in the synthesis of Mg_2FeH_6 . This finding opens new perspectives in the recycling of Fe-based metal wastes for synthesising low cost and sustainable hydrogen/energy storage materials possessing good capacities and excellent kinetic performances.

5 Discussion

In this chapter the results presented in Chapter 4 are discussed. Moreover, the different systems are compared in terms of their absorption/desorption behaviour and their applicability for the upscaling as hydrogen and heat storage material.

5.1 PXD

For all the investigated systems, the possibility to form Mg_2FeH_6 was proven (Figure 4.1, Figure 4.20 and Figure 4.12). In contrast to what is usually reported in literature ([27, 38, 44]), in most of the investigated cases the formation of MgH_2 upon hydrogenation was not detected or its diffraction peaks appeared to be extremely weak (Figure 4.9 or Figure 4.17). However, at the light of the results obtained with the other characterisation techniques, like DTA-MS measurements (e.g. Figure 4.3), we cannot exclude the presence of MgH_2 even in considerable *wt%* amounts. Thus, we could assume that the difficulties in detecting the presence of this phase via XRD arise from its high degree of nanostructuring due to the high energy milling that the material underwent during the synthesis process. In the desorption process, the single step phenomenon in the 316L (Figure 4.18) and M300 sample (Figure 4.27) follows the reaction scheme:

as reported from Gennari et al. and Polanski et al. [38, 77]. For the reference system a two step phenomenon, as reported from Puszkiel et al. is taking place [27].

The formation of an additional phase, which is visible both in the sample prepared with M300 (Figure 4.20) and 316L (Figure 4.12), can be attributed to the alloying elements of the steel. Peaks for this phase are also visible in the *in situ* PXD (see Figure 4.27 and Figure 4.17) and lead to the conclusion that the detected peaks consist of Mg and Ni.

5.2 Thermal Analyses

Results from the thermal analyses (only DTA curves) show a single endothermic event for all of the three samples (Figure 4.3, Figure 4.21 and Figure 4.13). Thus, it is reasonable to claim that macroscopically the decomposition process takes place in a single step. However, carefully looking at the DTA signal acquired for both, the sample synthesised with the steel 316L and M300, the peaks do not appear to be symmetrical (see Figure 4.15 and Figure 4.22, respectfully). This peculiarity is much more pronounced for the material synthesised with the 316L steel. It is likely that the overall DTA signal is the result of two distinct phenomena overlapping each other (two different decomposition events). This indicates that beside the Mg_2FeH_6 (visible in the XRD analyses) a second hydride phase such as MgH_2 (in nanostructured form) is present.

5.3 Volumetric Measurements

In order to consider a hydrogen storage material suitable for real scale application, the thermodynamic and kinetic properties as well as the storage capacity are of importance. Moreover, the properties (i.e. their values) should remain stable upon a large number of dehydrogenation/re-hydrogenation cycles. Although due to time constraints a thorough investigation of the material cycling behaviour was not possible, the first 10 dehydrogenating/re-hydrogenation cycles of all the investigated material were studied (with the exception for 316L where solely four cycles were performed). The volumetric investigation performed for the reference system (Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7) indicates that a small capacity decrease occurs after the 8th cycle, with the capacity still over 4.4 wt%. The slightly reduced capacity after cycling can be attributed to the solid-solid diffusion barriers which arise when, upon cycling, coarsening and segregation phenomena occur (see Figure 4.8). The hydrogenation/dehydrogenation kinetic behaviour of the M300 samples are faster than the one from the reference system (Figure 4.24 and Figure 4.25). This phenomenon is in good agreement with the findings of [Rzeszotarska et al.](#), which also noted faster kinetics of the samples prepared using steel instead of pure Fe [45]. This is most likely a consequence of the several TM elements that are alloyed together with Fe in the steel. In fact, it is well known that TMs and TM-based compounds act as catalyst for many hydrogen storage materials. In the case of MgH_2 formation, [Puszkiet et al.](#), [Welter and Rudman](#) and [Bogdanovic et al.](#) reported this phenomenon [27, 37, 78]. [Rzeszotarska et al.](#) and [Varin et al.](#) also reported on the catalytic effect of Ni and Fe on

the system [45, 79]. It is generally expected that faster kinetic behaviour is connected to lower values of activation energy. Thus, the sample prepared from M300 should possess a value of activation energy for the desorption process lower than that of the reference material (Mg_2FeH_6). Yet, this is not the case, since the reference possesses an activation energy of 100 ± 6 and M300 of 115 ± 3 , see Section 4. In fact, the M300 samples show improved kinetics over the reference, as reported in Section 4.3. In order to explain this phenomenon, another parameter, such as the kinetic constant, should be taken into account. The kinetic constant considers the probability of encounter of the particles. Furthermore, the kinetic constant provides information about the energy transfer between the particles during the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation.

Since the calculation of the activation energy does not take the pre-exponential factor into consideration, the meaningfulness of this value is not always given. Thus, looking at the kinetic constant using the Arrhenius Equation (5.2), the kinetics of the samples can be evaluated further.

$$k = A \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{R \cdot T}} \quad (5.2)$$

In this formula, k is the kinetic constant and A is the pre-exponential factor. The pre-exponential factor has to be determined prior to the calculation of the kinetic constant, which can be determined from the linear plotting with the following equation. The intercept is the value for the point where the graph of the linear plot intersects the y-axis of the coordinate system. Thus, where $x = 0$ is satisfied.

$$A = e^{\text{intercept}} * \frac{-E_a}{R} \quad (5.3)$$

In Table 5.1 the calculated values for the pre-exponential factor and for the kinetic constant are shown. Additionally, to make the kinetic constant a meaningful parameter, it can be multiplied with the maximum capacity to get a hint of the reaction rate.

Table 5.1: Results from the pre-exponential factor and the kinetic constant

Sample	$A / \frac{1}{s}$	$E_a / \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$	$k / \frac{1}{s}$	reaction rate $/ \frac{\text{wt}\%}{s}$
Reference	$4.86 \cdot 10^7$	100	0.8	3.82
316L	$9.66 \cdot 10^6$	87	1.7	4.42
M300	$7.35 \cdot 10^9$	115	8.7	24.2

The resulting reaction rate of M300 is six times higher than the one from the reference and about five times higher than the sample prepared with 316L. These values are in good agreement with the obtained results from the observed kinetics. For the system synthesised with the steel M300, a faster dehydrogenation was observed than for 316L and for the pristine Mg_2FeH_6 (Section 5.3). As stated in Equation (5.2), the pre-exponential factor causes an effect on the kinetic constant and thus resulting in an increase of the reaction rate.

5.4 Room Temperature Absorption

Nevertheless, thermal analyses after RT absorption show a different phenomenon. For the reference material a smaller, yet clearly visible, peak is occurring (Figure 4.11). Therefore, the decomposition proceeds in two steps, like reported from [Puszkiel et al.](#). Since the equilibrium pressure for MgH_2 is higher than for Mg_2FeH_6 , magnesium hydride is decomposing first. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that the driving force for dehydrogenation has to be larger to start before [27].

In the sample with 316L there seems to be an additional thermal event (Figure 4.19). The two main peaks contain almost the same intensity. Beforehand, there occurs a small shoulder part, which is also visible in the M300 system (Figure 4.28). Contrary to the 316L system, the DTA curve shows a single peak, leading to the conclusion, that the desorption occurs in a single step, as reported from [Polanski et al.](#).

From the DTA-MS analyses it is visible that hydrogen is released upon heating of the sample. Thus, FTIR measurements were performed to check if the absorption bands of MgH_2 and Mg_2FeH_6 are present. For the systems prepared from M300 and 316L it was not possible to collect high quality patterns which indicate the presence of Mg_2FeH_6 .

The obtained FTIR spectra (see Figure 5.1) suggests that also in the sample which was hydrogenated at RT, MgH_2 and Mg_2FeH_6 are present. Although the peak is not as intense as for the reference sample, it is still notable. The dashed grey lines indicate the peaks visible due to the machine set up, which can also be described as noise from the machine.

Figure 5.1: FT-IR of reference (Mg_2FeH_6) sample as prepared, MgH_2 and reference (Mg_2FeH_6) after RT absorption at 85 bar

The absorption at RT occurs for all the investigated samples (see Figures 4.11, 4.19 and 4.19). According to Lu et al., a RT absorption is also noticed for a slightly different system. An absorption at RT is possible due to the presence of nanocrystalline Mg. The investigated system in this case is Mg-Ti-H and, similar to the material preparation of the Mg-Fe-H system, the material was milled in a planetary mill under hydrogen pressure [80]. In the frame of the literature review for this thesis, this was the first time that the formation of MgH_2FeH_6 is reported to occur under such mild temperature conditions.

6 Conclusion

In this work, the Mg-Fe-H system, in form of the ternary complex hydride Mg_2FeH_6 , is investigated. Recently [Rzeszotarska et al.](#) successfully synthesised Mg_2FeH_6 using stainless steel 316L as the source of Fe. Starting from this publication, this thesis work thoroughly investigated the possibility to obtain high capacity high performance Mg_2FeH_6 using less pure material sources. Thus, the steels 316L and M300 were utilised, and the obtained results were compared with those of the pristine Mg_2FeH_6 system. Hence, a deeper scientific understanding on the effect of the utilisation of different Fe sources on the hydrogen sorption properties of the Mg-Fe-H system was reached. The synthesis of the samples consists of three steps. The first step is ball milling in a planetary mill, followed by a heat treatment. Both of the steps are performed under pressure in hydrogen atmosphere. The last step in the synthesis is performed in Ar atmosphere and consists of ball milling in a shaker mill.

Several characterisation techniques were used to investigate the kinetic and thermodynamic characteristics of the different samples. Thermal, volumetric, gravimetric as well as *in situ* and *ex situ* PXD investigations were performed on the synthesised materials. Mg_2FeH_6 was successfully synthesised with different sources of Fe. Aside from pure Fe, also the use of M300 and 316L lead to the formation of the ternary hydride. However, the hydrogen storage capacity of the materials synthesised using stainless steels is lower than that measured for the pure system. The system prepared from pure Fe leads to a gravimetric capacity of 4.78 wt% after the first cycle, whereas the samples prepared from 316L and M300 lead to capacities of 2.6 wt% and 2.78 wt% respectively.

In terms of reaction rate, the sample prepared with M300 showed faster hydrogen release than the sample prepared from 316L or pure Fe. In fact, for the material prepared using the M300 steel, the full hydrogenation just took three minutes. However, the full hydrogenation for the sample synthesised with 316L and the reference system (Mg_2FeH_6) took about four minutes and six minutes, respectively. The improved kinetic behaviour in presence of steel instead of pure Fe is in good agreement with the findings of [Rzeszotarska et al.](#).

Faster kinetic behaviour usually indicates lower activation energy. Nevertheless, results

obtained by thermal analyses showed a different pattern. The highest value for the activation energy was obtained for the sample synthesised from M300 with a value of $115 \pm 3 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$. The reference sample showed a value of $100 \pm 3 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$ and the sample prepared from 316L an activation energy of $87 \pm 3 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$. However, the dehydrogenation curves obtained in the volumetric device exhibited a faster behaviour for the samples synthesised with M300 in comparison with both the reference sample and the sample obtained with 316L. Therefore, further investigations on the nature of the observed kinetic behaviour were performed. In particular from the data obtained from the three different systems, the so called kinetic constant was calculated. The kinetic constant gives information about the energy transfer between the particles during the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation. In this regard, the calculation of the kinetic constant entails both the probability of encounter of the particles and the activation energy. The obtained results on the calculation of kinetic constants are in good agreement with the results found in the volumetric measurements. The reaction rate for the sample synthesised from M300 was six times higher than the one from the reference.

Owing to the fact that a room temperature absorption was observed during volumetric and gravimetric measurements, further investigations with DTA-MS analyses were conducted. Indeed, an absorption was taking place, since clear thermal events as well as a release of hydrogen was measured.

By means of the results of this work, the potential of using recycled materials was shown. In terms of cost reduction and sustainability, re-usage of materials is fundamental. Moreover, to meet the rising energy demand, development of energy storage systems, as well as hydrogen storage systems will get very important in the near future.

7 Outlook

As shown in Section 4 waste material, in form of M300 and 316L, can be used to substitute pure Fe. Hence, it would be of interest to investigate other steels as Fe substitution in this system. Therefore, alloys like Fe₄₀Al, IN625 or H13 might be considered. The composition of IN625 and H13 are displayed in Table A.1. H13 has, like M300, a martensitic crystal structure and contains significantly more Fe than the two steels investigated in this work. Therefore, their utilisation for the synthesis of Mg₂FeH₆ should be possible and the process to be followed should not differ much from the one reported in this work. The other alloy, IN625, is likely to form Mg₂NiH₄ which is known as a hydrogen storage material. This is due to the fact, that IN625 contains over 58 % Ni. Yet, since the formation of Mg₂FeH₆ is favoured over the formation of Mg₂NiH₄, Mg₂NiH₄ would solely form if enough Mg is present after the formation of Mg₂FeH₆ is completed. Moreover, introducing this material into the system, it would be of interest to investigate the effect of the formation of MgNi alloys in the system. As shown in Chapter 5 MgNi alloys were observed in this thesis as well.

Additionally, in Section 3.1.4 MgH₂ was synthesised successfully from Mg waste. Which indicates the possibility to completely substitute pure materials with waste materials for the synthesis of Mg₂FeH₆. It would be of interest to get further knowledge in systems which are prepared solely from waste materials. Therefore, the kinetic and thermodynamic behaviour should be further explored.

Since impurities tend to have an effect on the kinetic behaviour, as shown in Chapter 4, simulations of the system might provide further insight. Hence, the impact of impurities on the dehydrogenation energy in the Mg-Fe-H systems were calculated in a pre-study. As convergence for some structures could not be reached in the time frame of this thesis, some dehydrogenation energies could not be calculated, due to missing energy values. The simulations shown in this work have been conducted in collaboration with Tim Würger from the Institute for Polymer Composites from the Technical University of Hamburg (TUHH). For the simulations the software Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP) from the Vienna University was used [81]. Visualisation of the results were obtained by

using the software VESTA [82]. The *ab initio* calculation relies on the density functional theory (DFT), which can be used to calculate the electron structure of many-electron systems. Moreover, the results can be utilised to calculate e.g. the bonding energies. The reference system, Mg_2FeH_6 , was calculated first. To account for size effects due to periodic boundary conditions, a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ supercell was considered for the simulations. Hence, the dehydrogenation process can be expressed via Equation (7.1):

The overall energy, which is needed for the dehydrogenation, can be calculated using Equation (7.2) with $E_{\text{dehydrogenated}}$ as energy for the dehydrogenated system, $E_{\text{hydrogenated}}$ for the hydrogenated system, E_{H_2} for the isolated hydrogen molecule and ΔE the energy difference in eV.

$$\Delta E = E_{\text{dehydrogenated}} + \frac{1}{2}E_{\text{H}_2} - E_{\text{hydrogenated}} \quad (7.2)$$

In order to set up the unit cell, experimental data is required in terms of the crystal structure and the structure of the unit cell of the investigated material. Results obtained by PXD can assist in this process, since lattice parameters and further details are provided. Subsequent to the calculation of the pure system, one of the metal atoms can be exchanged with e.g. Ni or Cr in order to simulate the impact of the impurities, which are most available in the steels M300 and 316L. Since it is not known, which of the atoms in the pure Mg-Fe-H system is substituted by an impurity atom, all possible locations have to be considered. Consequently, for the Mg-Fe-H system the impurity atoms may replace Mg, Fe or can be located interstitially. Furthermore, to calculate the dehydrogenated system a hydrogen atom has to be removed. For this simulation, two different cases have been studied. In the first one, a hydrogen atom was removed which is located close to the inserted impurity atom. In the second case a hydrogen atom was removed which was located far away from the impurity atom. Thus, both cases have been calculated.

The results of the energy calculations can be seen in Table A.2. Negative values for the overall ΔE mean that the initial structure was less favourable. Thus, in the structure the hydrogen would relocate and move away from the impurity atom. The obtained values show that in the case of replacing an Fe atom (when the hydrogen atom is removed close to the impurity atom), hydrogen tends to bond stronger with Cr ($\Delta E = -0.90$ eV) than with a Ni ($\Delta E = -0.89$ eV) atom. Hence, the dehydrogenation in the case with the Ni atom would occur spontaneously, whereas in the case of the pure system ($\Delta E = -1.47$ eV) or

in the case with Cr, energy would have to be applied to the system for a dehydrogenation. In the following Figure 7.1a) an example for the unit cell with a Cr impurity is shown. Mg atoms are coloured in orange, Fe atoms in brown, hydrogen atoms in white, Ni in grey and Cr in blue. In the hydrogenated system the Cr replaces a Mg atom. In Figure 7.1b) a Ni atom replaces Mg.

Figure 7.1: Hydrogenated Mg-Fe-H unit cell

As mentioned, the impurities have an effect on the dehydrogenation energy. Yet, aspects like the behaviour at the surface of the metal upon dehydrogenation, diffusion barriers have not been taken into account. Furthermore, it might be useful to investigate where and how the dehydrogenating hydrogen atom is moving through the material. These aspects should be investigated further to get an appropriate idea of the impact of the steels and their alloying elements on the Mg-Fe-H system. Additionally, molecular dynamics may give an insight about formation of phases and the movement of the atoms upon hydrogenation/dehydrogenation. The obtained results are promising, yet there are still a lot of different aspects that should be studied in detail.

As shown in this thesis, employing waste material is a very appealing approach. Aside from lowering the production costs, it assists in the transition to a more sustainable world. Moreover, investigations in the heat storage and hydrogen storage sector will gain more focus in the future in order to meet the world's growing energy demand. Furthermore, simulations facilitate the investigation of material properties and assist in finding new synthesis paths or even materials.

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A Appendix

A.1 Fitting of Desorption Curves Cycling; Reference

Figure A.1: Linear fitting of 1st desorption curve; reference

Figure A.2: Linear fitting of 2nd desorption curve; reference

Figure A.3: Linear fitting of 3rd desorption curve; reference

Figure A.4: Linear fitting of 4th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.5: Linear fitting of 5th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.6: Linear fitting of 6th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.7: Linear fitting of 7th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.8: Linear fitting of 8th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.9: Linear fitting of 9th desorption curve; reference

Figure A.10: Linear fitting of 10th desorption curve; reference

A.2 Fitting of Desorption Curves Cycling; M300

Figure A.11: Linear fitting of 1st desorption curve; M300

Figure A.12: Linear fitting of 2nd desorption curve; M300

Figure A.13: Linear fitting of 3rd desorption curve; M300

Figure A.14: Linear fitting of 4th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.15: Linear fitting of 5th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.16: Linear fitting of 6th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.17: Linear fitting of 7th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.18: Linear fitting of 8th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.19: Linear fitting of 9th desorption curve; M300

Figure A.20: Linear fitting of 10th desorption curve; M300

A.3 Other Possible Fe Substitutions

Table A.1: Composition of IN625 and H13

Element	IN625		H13	
	Min /%	Max /%	Min /%	Max /%
Fe		5.00	87.00	
Ni	58.00			0.75
Cr	20.00	23.00	4.75	5.50
Mo	8.00	10.00	1.10	1.75
Nb (+Ta)	3.15	4.15		
C		0.10	0.32	0.45
Mn		0.50	0.20	0.60
Si		0.50	0.80	1.25
P		0.0015		0.03
S		0.0015		0.03
Al		0.40		
Ti		0.40		
Co (if determined)		1.00		
V			0.80	1.20
Cu				0.75

A.4 Simulation of the Dehydrogenation Energy

Table A.2: Energy values for different Mg_2FeH_6 structures; Reference, Ni, Cr

structure		ΔE /eV	
		close	far
Reference		1.47	
Ni	Mg replaced	0.28	
	Fe replaced	-0.89	1.02
	intercalated	0.67	1.43
Cr	Mg replaced	0.10	
	Fe replaced	0.90	1.29
	intercalated	0.34	0.94